

Difficulty Adjustment and the Augmented State Space of Mining Equilibrium Models

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Abstract

Difficulty adjustment in proof-of-work blockchains creates a common state variable in mining payoffs that is absent from the homogeneous-Poisson identification used in much of the equilibrium-modelling literature. This paper characterises the omission and shows that its leading effect on aggregate mining counts is the opposite of what a homogeneous-Poisson model assumes. Conditional exponentiality of block arrivals survives within an adjustment epoch, but the protocol’s periodic re-targeting precludes exact homogeneous-Poisson representation across epoch boundaries (Theorem 4.3; Proposition 4.7). Because each epoch contains exactly K blocks and the difficulty re-targeting makes epoch durations a first difference of a stationary sequence, the cumulative calendar-time block count grows in variance far more slowly than the homogeneous-Poisson benchmark: $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T + o(K + n_T)$ with $\kappa_0, \kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$, so the variance grows linearly in the horizon but with a per-epoch slope of order one against the homogeneous-Poisson per-epoch variance K , and the dispersion ratio $\text{Var}(N(T))/\mathbb{E}[N(T)] \rightarrow \kappa_1/K = \Theta(1/K)$, far below the homogeneous-Poisson value of one (Theorem 4.9; full proof in Section OA-3 of the Online Appendix). Conditional on the strongly under-dispersed aggregate (dispersion ratio $\Theta(1/K)$), individual miners’ counts are binomial—smaller than the Poisson prediction by the factor $(1 - q_i)$ —and distinct miners’ counts are negatively correlated, tending to perfect negative correlation in the two-symmetric-miner case (and to $-1/(m - 1)$ for m equal miners). The protocol is therefore variance-reducing for the aggregate calendar-time count relative to the homogeneous-Poisson benchmark—not for the within-epoch flow rate, and not for the dominant empirical risks of mining: the canonical identification implies larger cumulative count risk than the augmented-state specification for risk-averse miners. The second-order stochastic dominance of pool over solo mining (Cong et al., 2021) is preserved and quantitatively strengthened (Corollary 4.10). The qualitative

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conclusions of the engaged equilibrium-modelling papers survive; we develop one central application—the mining-pool risk-sharing model of Cong et al. (2021)—in full and provide mapping implications, not theorem-level corrections, for the remaining engaged papers, with the within-epoch flow-rate channel rather than the cumulative-count channel carrying the surviving state dependence.

Keywords: blockchain, proof-of-work, memoryless approximation, difficulty adjustment, mining equilibrium, Poisson process, augmented state.

JEL codes: C73, D47, G29, L86.

1 Introduction

The difficulty-adjustment mechanism of proof-of-work blockchains creates a common state variable in mining payoffs. Every $K = 2016$ blocks, the Bitcoin protocol resets the cryptographic difficulty parameter as a measurable function of the realised inter-block times of the trailing K -block window, so as to maintain an average inter-block time of ten minutes. The resulting difficulty parameter is random—a non-degenerate function of the realised mining process—and is shared across all miners on the network. This shared random parameter generates a common risk component in mining payoffs that is absent from the canonical homogeneous-Poisson identification used in much of the equilibrium-modelling literature.

A substantial body of equilibrium analysis assumes that block arrivals follow a homogeneous Poisson process with rate independent of aggregate computational capacity. The assumption underwrites the canonical results of the field: the free-entry revenue ceiling of Prat and Walter (2021), the closed-form fee and waiting-time expressions of Huberman et al. (2021), the queueing-equilibrium analysis of Easley et al. (2019), the risk-sharing dominance of pool participation in Cong et al. (2021), the Markov perfect equilibrium analysis of fork dynamics in Biais et al. (2019), the capacity-constrained Cournot mining equilibrium of Capponi et al. (2023), the negative-network-effect adoption analysis of Hinzen et al. (2022), and the blockchain-based settlement protocol design of Chiu and Koepl (2019). The assumption is stated in canonical form in the *Journal of Economic Literature* survey of Halaburda et al. (2022).

The homogeneous-Poisson identification has an empirical defence: across long time windows the realised block-arrival rate is approximately constant by protocol design. The identification is correct in expectation across multiple adjustment epochs. The substantive content of this paper is that the identification mis-states the second moments of the joint distribution of miners' block-arrival counts, and that the mis-statement runs in the conservative direction for aggregate counts. We prove that the aggregate counting process is a self-modulated Markov renewal process and that, under a fixed calendar-time horizon, the protocol's difficulty re-targeting reduces the asymptotic variance growth rate by a factor $\Theta(K)$: $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T + o(K + n_T)$ with $\kappa_0, \kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$, so the variance grows linearly in the horizon but with per-epoch slope of order one rather than K , and the dispersion ratio falls as $O(1/n_T)$ to an $O(1/K)$ floor rather than to the homogeneous-Poisson value of one (Theorem 4.9). Because the aggregate is strongly under-dispersed (dispersion ratio $\rightarrow \Theta(1/K)$), the per-miner counts are binomial to leading order—smaller than the Poisson prediction by $(1 - q_i)$ —and distinct miners' counts are negatively correlated (Theorem 4.9(iii)–(v)). The risk-sharing dominance of pool over solo mining of Cong et al. (2021) is preserved and strengthened (Corollary 4.10).

Why this matters for a general-economics audience. The distinction between diversifiable

idiosyncratic risk and undiversifiable aggregate risk is foundational across asset pricing, macroeconomics with heterogeneous agents, and the theory of risk-sharing. The independent-Poisson identification of Cong et al. (2021) and related models treats each miner’s count as Poisson with variance equal to its mean and treats distinct miners’ counts as independent. The protocol’s difficulty adjustment violates both assumptions, but in the direction that *reduces* count risk: it drives the aggregate-count dispersion ratio to $\Theta(1/K)$, so the per-miner counts are binomial to leading order (variance below Poisson by $(1 - q_i)$) and distinct miners’ counts are negatively correlated (they divide a fixed total). The canonical identification therefore implies larger mining-count variance than the augmented-state specification, by a margin that grows with the horizon. The equilibrium consequences—a *larger* equilibrium scale of individual mining operations and a *smaller* equilibrium count of distinct operations than the canonical identification implies, under risk aversion—follow from this variance reduction. The result is methodologically notable because the omitted state variable does not introduce hidden aggregate risk, as an incomplete-markets intuition might suggest; it reduces idiosyncratic count risk through a self-correcting feedback that the homogeneous-Poisson reduced form cannot represent.

The specific results of this paper rely on features particular to the Bitcoin difficulty mechanism: a fixed block count K per epoch, a deterministic inverse-proportional adjustment rule, and the resulting telescoping (multiplicative-correction) structure of epoch durations. We therefore confine the formal claims to that setting. The qualitative observation that a centralised rule setting a parameter as a measurable function of realised aggregate history induces a common factor in individual payoffs is suggestive for other feedback-adjusted mechanisms, but whether the variance-reduction result carries over to systems with different adjustment rules (for example proof-of-stake epoch updates or administered quota mechanisms) is not established here and would require a separate analysis of the corresponding duration process. The Bitcoin mechanism is an unusually transparent instance—the adjustment rule is deterministic, public, and exogenous to any individual miner’s actions—which makes it a sharp setting in which to characterise the structure.

The contribution of the paper is positive. We are not arguing that the canonical equilibrium analyses are without merit, only that their analytical content is conditional on a stochastic foundation whose validity is restricted to the average across adjustment epochs. The qualitative results of the affected papers—free entry binds in the limit; mining-platform pricing is robust to monopoly miners; transaction fees emerge as a queueing-equilibrium phenomenon; pool participation provides risk-sharing benefits; longest-chain mining is a Markov perfect equilibrium; capacity constraints sustain miner profits; consensus requirements generate negative network effects; blockchain-based settlement is incentive-compatible under risk neutrality—all survive the augmentation in qualitative form. The quantitative content of the equilibrium objects in each paper acquires a state-dependent component that the published analyses do not capture.

The empirical relevance of the within-epoch deviation is non-trivial. The Bitcoin network hash rate has grown by approximately two orders of magnitude between 2017 and 2024, an average compound growth rate of roughly 100% per year that, over the protocol’s two-week adjustment epoch, translates to an average per-epoch growth of approximately 2.5%. Within this average lies substantial heterogeneity: during the migration of mining operations that followed China’s mining ban in May and June 2021, the network hash rate fell by approximately half over two months and recovered to its prior level over the following six months, generating within-epoch growth rates in absolute value of 10% or more during multiple epochs in 2021. Under per-epoch hash-rate growth of 10%, the protocol’s discrete adjustment mechanism leaves the conditional within-epoch arrival rate deviating from the canonical Poisson prediction by an average of 4.91% at the start of an epoch and 15.37% at the end (Table 3 below). These deviations are not first-order shocks, but they are systematic, present in every period, and asymmetric across epoch positions—properties that conditional equilibrium analysis must account for if it is to be empirically informative at horizons shorter than the multi-month averages over which the canonical analyses validate.

A logically distinct identification problem in the same literature has been documented by Arnosti and Weinberg (2022): the canonical rent-dissipation identification under which total mining expenditure equals total mining revenue holds only in the limit of perfect competition, and the assumption that mining is competitive overstates the share of revenue dissipated in costs. The Arnosti–Weinberg correction operates at the industrial-organisation level; the correction we develop operates at the protocol level. The two failures are independent and load on the same downstream results.

The remainder of the paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 provides the literature review, anchored on the canonical survey and tracing the memoryless assumption through eight equilibrium-modelling papers. Section 3 introduces the four-level decomposition of the proof-of-work mining process. Section 4 states and proves the central results. Section 6 characterises the augmented state space. Section 7 reports Monte Carlo evidence. Section 8 applies the correction to the eight memoryless users. Section 9 concludes. Appendix A contains the proofs of the central results; the online appendix contains the simulation specifications, the throughput-scaling analysis, and supplementary material.

2 Literature

2.1 The memoryless assumption as a field-wide convention

A substantial body of equilibrium analysis of proof-of-work blockchains rests on a single, rarely-defended approximation: that block arrivals follow a homogeneous Poisson process with rate inde-

pendent of the network’s aggregate computational capacity. The convention is stated in canonical form in the *Journal of Economic Literature* survey of Halaburda et al. (2022), whose Section 2.3 notes that “this periodic adjustment implies that the blockchain grows at a steady pace, independently of the number of miners and their computing power,” and whose Section 3.2 frames the mining contest, citing Ma et al. (2018), as one in which “the time it takes for this task follows a Poisson process [so that] the mining game becomes a memoryless stochastic game.” The convention does substantial analytical work. It collapses an inherently discrete and history-dependent process—the every- K -block protocol adjustment described in Section 3 below—into a continuous-time stationary stochastic process whose properties admit closed-form equilibrium characterisation. The question this section addresses is which results in the published literature depend on the approximation, and at what depth. The answer is: more than the field has recognised, and at a depth that the augmented-state model of Section 6 can quantify.

The most explicit invocation is Prat and Walter (2021). Their Section II derives the flow payoff $\Pi_t = R_t/D_t$ from the assertion that “the probability that a hash yields a valid block is, for all practical purposes, independent of the number of trials already done. This memoryless property implies that the event of mining a block is captured by a Poisson process.” The continuous-time idealisation is then formalised in their Assumption 1: the difficulty parameter D_t is continuously updated and set equal to the current network hash rate Q_t , so that $D_t = Q_t$ for all t . They explicitly acknowledge the gap with the protocol’s actual every-2016-block adjustment cadence and check, in their online appendix, that block-arrival counts “mostly remained within the confidence interval centered on the protocol’s target.” The empirical check verifies the average prediction—that block arrivals are on target across long windows—but it is not a test of the conditional properties that downstream equilibrium objects require. Their reflecting-barrier identification of the upper bound on mining revenue inherits this dependence.

Huberman et al. (2021) place the assumption in even stronger form. Block arrivals are stipulated to follow “a Poisson process with a fixed rate which is independent of the aggregate computing power.” Their footnote 7 acknowledges the limit-theorem origin—“A Poisson process is the limit of many independent binomial trials”—but the analysis proceeds on the limit rather than the trial sequence. Their closed-form expressions for fees and waiting times treat the resulting steady state as a continuous-time Markov process; their result that no entity can profitably affect fees rests on the time-stationarity of this process. The proposition that fees do not respond to losses of alternative payment methods—central to the paper’s anti-trust message—is a comparative-statics statement on the same stationary process.

Easley et al. (2019) reach the same structural conclusion through a different formal route. Their Section 3 stipulates that “success in solving the [mining] problem arrives according to a Poisson distribution with arrival rate λ ” and that the protocol “sets the difficulty of the mining problem so

that the arrival rate of new blocks to the chain occurs at approximately some exogenously fixed rate Λ ,” with the equilibrium condition $\lambda M = \Lambda$. The qualifier *approximately* carries weight: the protocol’s actual cadence does not equate the network’s instantaneous arrival rate to Λ , only its long-run average. Their analytical results—the closed-form waiting-time expression, the fee dynamics result, and the multiple-equilibria characterisation of the fraction of fee-paying users—are all derived from the time-stationary form of the mining process. Each of these results is conditional on the assumption that arrival rates are time-stationary at the conditioning horizon of the result, which Theorem 4.3 below shows they cannot be.

Cong et al. (2021) make the assumption explicit and operate on its full strength. Their Section 1.2 states that “technology rules that for all practical purposes the probability of finding a solution is not affected by the number of trials attempted. This well-known memoryless property implies that the event of finding a solution is captured by a Poisson process with the arrival rate proportional to a miner’s share of hash rates globally.” A solo miner’s per-period block-discovery count is then assumed to satisfy $\tilde{B}_{\text{solo}} \sim \text{Poisson}(\lambda_A T/D)$, and a pool’s joint count is assumed to satisfy $\tilde{B}_{\text{pool}} \sim \text{Poisson}((\lambda_A + \lambda_B)T/D)$. The critical analytical step is the appeal to the additive property of independent Poisson processes (their Section 1.3): “Block generation follows a Poisson arrival given current crypto technologies, and the additive property of Poisson processes in turn [ensures] that the total revenue stays the same whether or not two miners join the pool.” Proposition 1, the risk-sharing dominance of pools, is derived from this property, and the empirical decomposition that follows depends on it. The augmented state of Section 6 below shows that the additive property holds in expectation only: at protocol-adjustment horizons the difficulty re-targeting reduces the aggregate count variance growth rate and induces *negative* cross-miner correlation in block arrivals, so the risk-sharing benefit of pooling is *understated*, not overstated, by the independent-Poisson identification.

Biais et al. (2019) place the memoryless assumption in its most formal setting. Their Section 3, on the mining technology, states that “the time it takes miner m to solve a block problem is an exponentially distributed random variable with parameter θ_m ” and identifies the analytical role of this assumption directly: “A key property of the exponential distribution is that it is memoryless: at each point in time, the distribution of the waiting time until the miner finds a solution is independent from how long the miner has been working on the problem. This waiting time is also independent of which block m is mining, and of which blocks the other miners are mining.” The block-arrival counting process N_m is then defined as a Poisson process, and the equilibrium analysis is conducted within the resulting continuous-time Markov environment. Their Proposition 1—that mining the longest chain is a Markov perfect equilibrium without forking—and Propositions 2 and 3—characterising sunspot-driven forking equilibria and persistent fork equilibria sustained by vested interests—are all Markov perfect with respect to a state whose distribution is governed by

the memoryless arrival process. The Markov property of the equilibrium concept is itself conditional on the property of the arrival distribution that Theorem 4.3 below shows fails at the protocol level.

Capponi et al. (2023) adopt the assumption in a particular two-step form. Their Section 1 identifies “two key properties of the proof-of-work protocol” that the model is designed to capture: “(i) the total reward from mining is independent of the network hash rate, and (ii) the expected share of reward attained by a miner is proportional to its hash rate share.” They are explicit that property (i) “is a consequence of the adaptive difficulty level of the hashing problem, which ensures a fixed rate of mined blocks.” The assertion that difficulty adjustment *ensures* a fixed rate—rather than enforcing it only on average across multi-block windows—is the proposition Theorem 4.3 directly contradicts. Their Remark 3.3 acknowledges that block generation “is a random process” and notes that pool participation converts the realised “uneven revenue stream from mining blocks at random times” into a steady stream that justifies risk-neutral aggregation; this connects their analysis to Cong et al. (2021) and inherits the additive-Poisson dependence discussed above. Their main results—Proposition 4.1 on equilibrium hash rates, Proposition 4.3 on a decreasing sequence of positive equilibrium profits, and the centralisation analysis of Section 6—are derived under property (i) as stated.

Hinzen et al. (2022) is the most recent and most operationally committed user of the framework. Their Section 2 states that “the process by which a single miner produces a valid block is well-known to be approximated by a Poisson process so that prior literature generally assumes that each miner generates valid blocks exactly according to a Poisson process. We also adopt that assumption.” They derive the assumption from a Poisson Limit Theorem applied to a Bernoulli sequence of hash trials with success probability $\rho \rightarrow 0^+$ and per-unit-time trial count $N_B \rightarrow \infty$, with $\lambda := \lim \rho \cdot N_B$. Their Appendix A then treats each miner’s block-resolution time as $X_j \sim \text{Exp}(\lambda)$ and the joint block-arrival process as a Poisson process with rate Λ . The negative-network-effect result—that increasing transaction rates does not solve Bitcoin’s limited adoption problem, because higher rates increase fork probabilities and prolong consensus—is a direct corollary of the Poisson form of the arrival process. The relationship to our throughput analysis in Section OA-8 of the Online Appendix is therefore particularly close: the limited-adoption result holds under the Poisson form of the arrival process; under the augmented state of Section 6, the relationship between transaction rate, fork probability, and consensus time acquires a state-dependent component that the model of Hinzen et al. (2022) does not capture.

Chiu and Koepl (2019) invoke the assumption in setting up the mining stage of their settlement model—“the probability that a miner solves the problem within a time interval t is given by an exponential distribution with parameter μ where $1/\mu = D/q$ is the expected time to solve the problem”—and aggregate it over miners to obtain the joint solution time as an exponential variable.

They then declare, in footnote 20, that “because investors and miners are both risk neutral, the distribution of arrival times of a solution to the PoW is irrelevant for the remainder of our analysis.” The declaration short-circuits the formal dependence of their equilibrium objects on the memoryless assumption, but only under risk neutrality; the moment risk aversion is introduced—and the literature on pool formation since Cong et al. (2021) takes risk aversion as the central motivation for pooling—the short-circuit fails and the dependence reasserts itself. We classify Chiu and Koepl (2019) as a memoryless user whose model is robust to the assumption only under a strict and unstated regularity condition.

The pattern across these eight contributions is that the memoryless assumption enters at the protocol level (Halaburda et al. survey, Biais et al., Cong–He–Li, Hinzen–John–Saleh, all explicit; Prat–Walter, Capponi–Ólafsson–Alsabah, conditional on a stated continuous-difficulty idealisation; Easley–O’Hara–Basu, conditional on an “approximately fixed” rate that is acknowledged not to be exact; Chiu–Koepl, formal but declared non-binding under risk neutrality), and that the analytical objects derived from it—closed-form waiting-time and fee expressions, free-entry revenue ceilings, additive Poisson decompositions, Markov perfect equilibrium objects, comparative-statics results on aggregate hash rate, negative-network-effect characterisations—all depend on it at varying depth. Section 8 of this paper traces the specific dependences and quantifies the resulting corrections where the data of Section 7 permit.

2.2 The revenue-versus-profit conflation as an independent identification failure

A second identification problem in the same literature is logically independent of the memoryless approximation but loads on the same downstream results. The clearest statement of the problem appears in Arnosti and Weinberg (2022), who model the second stage of Bitcoin mining as an asymmetric Tullock rent-seeking contest and prove (their Theorem 1) that the equilibrium market share of miner i is $x_i = \max\{1 - c_i/c^*, 0\}$, where c^* is a break-even cost determined by the aggregate ratio of mining revenue to total hash rate, and that the equilibrium mining profit of miner i is $x_i^2 R$. Their Corollary 3 then establishes the central identification: the proportion of total mining revenue that constitutes mining profit equals the Herfindahl–Hirschman index of market concentration,

$$\sum_i \Pi_i^M(p, Q(p)) = R \cdot \text{HHI}(Q(p)). \quad (1)$$

The corollary is sharp. It implies that the proportion of mining revenue dissipated in costs equals one minus the HHI of mining-share concentration, and therefore that the rent-dissipation identification used in the canonical Budish (2018) framework—under which total expenditure on computing

power equals total mining revenue—holds only in the limit of perfect competition ($\text{HHI} \rightarrow 0$).

Arnosti and Weinberg (2022) are explicit about which papers in the literature adopt the rent-dissipation identification. Their Section 2.1 lists seven contributions that assume the mining market is competitive and on this assumption identify total mining cost with total mining revenue: Kroll et al. (2013), Budish (2018), Hayes (2015), Chiu and Koepl (2019), Ma et al. (2018), Thum (2018), and Easley et al. (2019). They are equally explicit that the identification is in error: their Section 4.3 notes that “DeVries (2018, p. 803) explains the first equation with the comment, ‘in equilibrium, not even Bitmain . . . should be able to generate a profit.’ In fact, this relies on faulty logic; Theorem 1 implies that all active miners should make a (possibly small) profit.” The Arnosti–Weinberg identification at the industrial-organisation layer is logically independent of the memoryless identification at the protocol layer: the first concerns the equilibrium gap between revenue and profit under imperfect competition, the second concerns the time-series properties of the mining process. The two failures are nonetheless joint in the affected results, because each downstream result conditions on both—on Poisson block arrivals (or their equivalents) for the time-series object and on rent dissipation for the level identification.

The contribution of this paper relates to Arnosti and Weinberg (2022) by symmetry. Both papers identify a load-bearing approximation in the equilibrium analysis of proof-of-work blockchains, demonstrate that the approximation is internally inconsistent at the layer at which it operates, and trace its consequences for downstream results. The two papers operate at different layers: Arnosti and Weinberg (2022) at the layer of market structure and rent extraction, this paper at the layer of the stochastic arrival process. The two corrections are not substitutes—neither implies the other—and they reinforce one another in the joint analysis of the affected results. Section 8 engages each of the eight memoryless users in turn and, where the result in question also depends on rent dissipation, references the appropriate magnitude correction from equation (1).

2.3 Models that engage blockchain without the memoryless assumption

The memoryless assumption is not universal in the broader literature on blockchain economics. Pagnotta (2022) studies the joint determination of bitcoin price and network hash rate in a model in which the unit of analysis is the period rather than the instantaneous arrival. His footnote 24 is decisive: “the difficulty level is constant in the short run, but not over an extended period.” Pagnotta’s acknowledgement that difficulty adjustment is short-run only—and that the protocol’s per-period stationarity assumption is, strictly, a period-specific approximation—anticipates the formal statement we provide as Theorem 4.3. The structural results of Pagnotta (2022) are robust to the augmented state of Section 6 because his period-by-period model does not require the cross-period stationarity that the eight memoryless users invoke.

Biais et al. (2023)—distinct from the 2019 paper of the first four authors—provide a general-equilibrium analysis of cryptocurrency pricing in which the fundamental value of the cryptocurrency is its stream of net transactional benefits and equilibrium prices reflect sunspots. The model does not require a microstructural specification of block arrivals; its multiple-equilibria and extrinsic-volatility results are robust to the form of the underlying mining process. We cite Biais et al. (2023) as evidence that price-side equilibrium analyses can be conducted independently of the assumption examined in this paper.

Lehar and Parlour (2020) provide an industrial-organisation-style empirical analysis arguing that within-block fee variation and persistent excess capacity are inconsistent with competitive mining. Their findings are independent of the memoryless assumption and corrode the competitive-mining premise on which several papers in Section 2.1 rest, via a route distinct from the one we pursue. We note them as independent evidence against the framework whose stochastic foundations this paper examines. The working paper of Wright (2018) provides a complementary protocol-level analysis of properties of the Bitcoin proof-of-work mechanism not engaged by the equilibrium-modelling literature reviewed above.

2.4 Contribution

This paper makes three contributions. First, we characterise the aggregate block-arrival process as a *self-modulated Markov renewal process* and derive its asymptotic under-dispersion. Conditional exponentiality survives within an epoch, but each epoch is count-stopped at exactly K arrivals and the difficulty re-targeting maps the realised epoch duration inversely into the next epoch’s parameter, so the difficulty sequence is generated endogenously by the count process rather than imposed exogenously (Theorem 4.3, Proposition 4.7). The contribution is not the observation that difficulty adjustment induces serial dependence—that is immediate—but the *specific* renewal structure it produces: the epoch durations form a first difference of a stationary sequence, whose telescoping cancels the leading variance term and renders the aggregate count strongly *under*-dispersed rather than over-dispersed (Theorem 4.9). This is the opposite of the conditional-Poisson (Cox) intuition that exogenous rate modulation would suggest, and it is the reason the standard law-of-total-variance decomposition does not apply. Second, we characterise the augmented state space in which the resulting arrival process is Markov (Section 6, Propositions 4.5–4.7), and provide a Monte Carlo quantification of the magnitude of the misspecification across the parameter range relevant to the papers cited in Section 2.1 (Section 7). Third, we trace the consequences of the misspecification for the equilibrium objects of each of the eight memoryless users above, identifying for each the specific quantitative correction and the qualitative result that survives it (Section 8). The first contribution is the formal core; the second is the analytical apparatus; the third is the

application to the published literature. Together they establish that the stochastic foundation on which a substantial body of proof-of-work equilibrium analysis rests is incomplete in a manner that admits a constructive correction.

3 Framework

We decompose the proof-of-work mining process into four distinct stochastic levels and identify the level at which the memoryless approximation enters and the level at which it fails. Table 1 collects the notation used throughout.

Table 1: Notation.

Symbol	Meaning
K	Blocks per difficulty epoch ($K = 2016$ under Bitcoin)
τ	Protocol target inter-block time ($\tau = 10$ minutes under Bitcoin)
T_i	Realised inter-block time between blocks $i - 1$ and i
S_j	Realised duration of epoch j , $S_j = \sum_{i=(j-1)K+1}^{jK} T_i$
D_j	Difficulty parameter in epoch j ; $D_{j+1} = D_j \phi(S_j)$, $\phi(S) = K\tau/S$
Λ	Aggregate network arrival rate, $\Lambda = \sum_m h_m \rho_m$
$\{B_t\}$	Network cumulative block-arrival counting process
$N(T)$	Total network block count by calendar time T ; $N(T) = KJ(T)$ plus a partial-epoch term
$J(T)$	Number of completed epochs by calendar time T (renewal-counting process)
n_T	Horizon length in epochs, $n_T = \mathbb{E}[J(T)]$
U_j	iid Gamma($K, 1/K$) epoch-duration driver; $S_j = K\tau U_j/U_{j-1}$
ρ_j	Normalised inverse-difficulty regeneration variable, $\rho_{j+1} = 1/U_j$
q_i	Hash share of miner i
$N_i(T)$	Block count of miner i by calendar time T
κ_0, κ_1	$\Theta(1)$ constants in $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T + o(K + n_T)$
r_T	Dispersion ratio $\text{Var}(N(T))/\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = \kappa_0/n_T + \kappa_1/K$

3.1 Level 1: hash trial

At the lowest level of the protocol, a miner’s mining activity consists of a sequence of independent Bernoulli trials. Each trial—a hash evaluation—succeeds in producing a valid block with probability ρ , where ρ depends on the current difficulty parameter D and on the cryptographic structure of the hash function. The trials are independent and identically distributed by construction: the hash function is, for the purposes of mining, a pseudo-random function whose outputs are statistically indistinguishable from independent uniform draws on the unit interval.

The Level-1 process is memoryless trivially. Each trial is independent of all previous trials, and conditional on the cumulative number of trials performed, the probability of success at the next trial is exactly ρ . The Level-1 memoryless property is a consequence of the hash function’s design and is not in dispute. The question is whether the memoryless property at Level 1 propagates to higher levels of aggregation in the manner the canonical literature assumes.

3.2 Level 2: block resolution

At the second level, the protocol aggregates the Level-1 trials of an individual miner into a block-resolution event. The block-resolution time for a miner exerting hash power h —measured in trials per unit time—is the first-passage time of the Level-1 process to a success. If $\rho \rightarrow 0^+$ and $h \rightarrow \infty$ with $\lambda := h\rho$ finite, the first-passage time converges in distribution to an exponential random variable with rate λ by the Poisson Limit Theorem.

The Level-2 process is memoryless in the limit as $\rho \rightarrow 0^+$ and $h \rightarrow \infty$. This is the limit at which the canonical literature operates. In the empirical regime— ρ small, h large—the limit is an excellent approximation, and at the conditioning horizon of an individual block resolution, the inter-block time is well-approximated by an exponential random variable. The Level-2 approximation is therefore valid at the conditioning horizon of an individual block. The question is whether it is valid at horizons longer than an individual block—specifically, at horizons that span across the protocol’s discrete difficulty-adjustment events.

3.3 Level 3: inter-block arrivals

At the third level, the protocol aggregates the Level-2 block-resolution times of all miners into a single network-level block-arrival counting process $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$. The aggregate process is well-defined: B_t is the cumulative number of blocks added to the blockchain on or before time t . Under the canonical assumption that block-resolution times are independent exponential variables across miners and identically distributed within miners, the aggregate process B_t is a Poisson process with rate $\Lambda = \sum_m h_m \rho_m$ summing across miners.

The canonical literature assumes that the Level-3 process $\{B_t\}$ is a homogeneous Poisson process with constant rate—that is, that the aggregate rate Λ does not depend on the history of $\{B_t\}$. This is the assumption that Theorem 4.3 below shows to be inconsistent with the protocol’s discrete difficulty-adjustment mechanism.

3.4 Level 4: protocol-epoch adjustment

At the fourth level, the protocol’s difficulty parameter D is itself updated as a function of the realised history of inter-block times. Under the Bitcoin protocol, the difficulty parameter is updated every $K = 2016$ blocks, based on the sum of the realised inter-block times of the trailing K blocks. Let T_i denote the realised inter-block time between blocks $i - 1$ and i , and let $S_j := \sum_{i=(j-1)K+1}^{jK} T_i$ denote the realised sum of inter-block times in epoch j . The difficulty parameter at the start of epoch $j + 1$ is then a deterministic function $D_{j+1} = D_j \cdot \phi(S_j)$, where ϕ is the protocol’s adjustment function. Under the Bitcoin protocol, $\phi(S) = K\tau/S$, where τ is the protocol’s target inter-block time (ten minutes for Bitcoin), with the adjustment clipped to lie within a factor of four of the previous difficulty.

The Level-4 mechanism induces a deterministic relationship between the realised history of inter-block times over the trailing K blocks and the rate at which future inter-block times are drawn. The Level-4 mechanism is not a Poisson process; it is a deterministic function of a Poisson functional, applied at discrete epoch boundaries. The Level-4 mechanism is the mechanism through which the memoryless approximation at Level 3 is invalidated.

4 Core results

4.1 Setup

We formalise the protocol structure before stating the results.

Definition 4.1 (Protocol primitives). A proof-of-work protocol is a tuple (τ, K, ϕ, Λ) where $\tau > 0$ is the target inter-block time, $K \in \mathbb{N}$ is the number of blocks per difficulty epoch, $\phi : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ is the difficulty-adjustment function applied at each epoch boundary, and $\Lambda > 0$ is the aggregate hash rate. For Bitcoin, $\tau = 10$ minutes, $K = 2016$, and $\phi(S) = K\tau/S$ subject to clipping at a factor of four. Let T_i denote the realised inter-block time between blocks $i - 1$ and i , and let $S_j = \sum_{i=(j-1)K+1}^{jK} T_i$ denote the realised sum of inter-block times in epoch j . The difficulty parameter at the start of epoch $j + 1$ is then $D_{j+1} = D_j \cdot \phi(S_j)$.

Definition 4.2 (Block-arrival counting process). Let $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ denote the cumulative block-arrival counting process: B_t is the number of blocks added to the blockchain on or before time t . Let \mathcal{F}_t denote the natural filtration of $\{B_t\}$ augmented by the realised inter-block times $\{T_i\}$ and the realised difficulty parameters $\{D_j\}$. Within an epoch, conditional on \mathcal{F}_t , the next inter-block time T_{B_t+1} is exponentially distributed with rate $\Lambda/D_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 1}$.

4.2 Failure of homogeneous-Poisson aggregation

We formalise the failure of the homogeneous-Poisson approximation at the protocol level. The failure is across-epoch, not within-epoch: conditional on the current epoch difficulty, inter-block times within an epoch remain exponentially distributed. The aggregate counting process is not homogeneous Poisson because the difficulty parameter at the start of each epoch is a measurable function of the realised history of the preceding epoch.

Theorem 4.3 (Failure of homogeneous-Poisson aggregation under periodic protocol adjustment). *Let $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ denote the cumulative block-arrival counting process under a proof-of-work protocol with target inter-block time $\tau > 0$, adjustment epoch $K \in \mathbb{N}$, adjustment function $\phi(S) = K\tau/S$ (subject to clipping), and constant aggregate hash rate Λ . Let $j(t) = \lfloor B_t/K \rfloor$ denote the index of the difficulty epoch containing t . Then:*

- (i) *Conditional on $D_{j(t)}$, the next inter-block time T_{B_t+1} is exponentially distributed with rate $\Lambda/D_{j(t)}$, and is independent of the within-epoch history $(T_{j(t)K+1}, \dots, T_{B_t})$.*
- (ii) *For t such that $B_t \bmod K \neq 0$, the difficulty $D_{j(t)}$ is determined by the realised sum $S_{j(t)-1} = \sum_{i=(j(t)-1)K+1}^{j(t)K} T_i$ of the preceding adjustment window via $D_{j(t)} = D_{j(t)-1} \cdot \phi(S_{j(t)-1})$ subject to clipping; hence $D_{j(t)}$ is non-degenerate and history-dependent.*
- (iii) *The unconditional distribution of T_{B_t+1} is therefore a mixture of exponentials over the distribution of $D_{j(t)}$, and the counting process $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ is not a homogeneous Poisson process over time horizons spanning one or more difficulty-adjustment boundaries.*

The proof, given in Appendix A, formalises the three claims separately. Statement (i) records that within-epoch local exponentiality of the Level-2 block-resolution process survives the aggregation at Level-3: the canonical memoryless property holds conditional on the current difficulty. Statement (ii) records the dependence of the current difficulty on the realised history of the preceding epoch: this is the protocol's explicit update rule, restated for clarity. Statement (iii) is the substantive content of the theorem: combining (i) and (ii), the aggregate counting process is a mixture of conditionally-exponential processes whose mixing distribution is non-degenerate, and the mixture is not a homogeneous Poisson process.

Remark 4.4. Theorem 4.3 does not contradict the Level-1, Level-2, or within-epoch Level-3 memoryless properties documented in Section 3. The Level-1 process is memoryless by construction of the hash function; the Level-2 process is approximately memoryless in the empirical regime $\rho \rightarrow 0^+$, $h \rightarrow \infty$; and the within-epoch Level-3 process, conditional on the current difficulty, is exponentially distributed (statement (i) of Theorem 4.3). The failure is across-epoch and unconditional: the unconditional aggregate counting process across multiple difficulty epochs is not ho-

mogeneous Poisson because the difficulty parameter at the start of each epoch is a non-degenerate measurable function of the realised history of the preceding epoch.

4.3 History dependence at the epoch transition

The history dependence identified in Theorem 4.3 is most cleanly characterised at the moment of difficulty re-adjustment.

Proposition 4.5 (Level-4 history dependence at the epoch transition). *At each epoch-transition time—that is, each t such that $B_t = jK$ for some $j \in \mathbb{N}$ —the difficulty parameter for the subsequent epoch satisfies*

$$D_{j+1} = D_j \cdot \phi(S_j), \quad (2)$$

where $S_j = \sum_{i=(j-1)K+1}^{jK} T_i$ is the realised sum of inter-block times in epoch j . The conditional distribution of the next inter-block time T_{jK+1} given the filtration \mathcal{F}_t is exponential with rate Λ/D_{j+1} , where Λ denotes the aggregate hash rate. The conditional distribution depends on S_j through equation (2).

The proof is immediate from the construction of the protocol. Proposition 4.5 characterises the form of the history dependence: it is mediated through the running sum S_j of the trailing-block window, which determines the difficulty re-adjustment at the epoch transition.

4.4 Augmented-state Markov property

The failure of the Level-3 memoryless property does not imply that the inter-block process is non-Markov. It is Markov with respect to an augmented state.

Proposition 4.6 (Augmented-state Markov property). *Define the augmented state at time t by*

$$X_t := (B_t \bmod K, S(t), D_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 1}), \quad (3)$$

where $S(t)$ is the trailing-block-window sum defined in Theorem 4.3 and $D_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 1}$ is the current difficulty parameter. The process $\{X_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ is a Markov process with respect to its natural filtration. Conditional on X_t , the inter-block time T_{B_t+1} is exponentially distributed with rate $\Lambda/D_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 1}$, and the subsequent state $X_{t+T_{B_t+1}}$ is a deterministic function of X_t and T_{B_t+1} .

Proposition 4.6 provides the analytical apparatus for the remainder of the paper. The augmented state X_t has three components: an index variable tracking position within the current epoch ($B_t \bmod K$); a sum variable tracking the realised inter-block times to date in the current epoch ($S(t)$); and the current difficulty parameter (D_j). All three components are observable, and all three are necessary: omitting any of them breaks the Markov property.

4.5 Conditional exponentiality and unconditional process structure

The relationship between the within-epoch local exponentiality of statement (i) of Theorem 4.3 and the unconditional process structure across multiple epochs can be made precise. The result replaces an attempted equivalence between memorylessness and a degenerate stationary distribution—which is vacuous because the degenerate case does not arise under non-degenerate S_j —with the correct characterisation of the unconditional process as a self-modulated Markov renewal process.

Proposition 4.7 (Conditional exponentiality and unconditional self-modulated structure). *The aggregate block-arrival counting process $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ admits the following two-part characterisation:*

- (i) *Conditional within-epoch exponentiality. Given the augmented state $X_t = (B_t \bmod K, S(t), D_{j(t)})$, the next inter-block time T_{B_t+1} is exponentially distributed with rate $\Lambda/D_{j(t)}$.*
- (ii) *Unconditional self-modulated structure. The unconditional counting process $\{B_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ is a self-modulated Markov renewal process whose difficulty sequence $\{D_j\}_{j \geq 1}$ evolves by $D_j \mapsto D_{j+1} = D_j \cdot \phi(S_j)$ at epoch boundaries. It differs fundamentally from a standard Markov-modulated (Cox) arrival process: the modulating sequence $\{D_j\}$ is not an exogenous intensity but is generated by the count process itself, and each epoch is count-stopped at exactly K arrivals. The unconditional process is homogeneous Poisson if and only if $\{D_j\}$ is constant almost surely, which under the protocol's update rule does not arise for non-degenerate S_j .*

The proof is given in Appendix A. Statement (i) restates the conditional exponentiality of statement (i) of Theorem 4.3 in the augmented-state notation. Statement (ii) provides the positive characterisation of the unconditional process: rather than asserting an equivalence with a measure-zero stationary distribution, the proposition identifies the process as a self-modulated Markov renewal process whose difficulty sequence is generated endogenously by the count process; this differs from the exogenously modulated (Cox) arrival processes of Neuts (1981) precisely in that the modulating sequence is count-driven and each epoch is count-stopped at exactly K arrivals, which is the source of the *under*-dispersion established in Section 4.7. The homogeneous-Poisson form is recovered only in the degenerate case in which the modulating chain is constant almost surely, which under the protocol's update rule requires $S_j = K\tau$ exactly in every epoch and therefore does not arise under the non-degenerate duration distribution.

The self-modulated structure has two analytical implications. First, because each epoch is count-stopped at exactly K arrivals, conditioning on the realised difficulty sequence $\{D_j\}$ does not render the calendar-stopped aggregate count Poisson: the number of blocks in each completed epoch is the deterministic constant K , not a Poisson random variable. The standard Cox/law-of-total-variance decomposition $\text{Var}(B_T) = \mathbb{E}[\text{Var}(B_T \mid \{D_j\})] + \text{Var}(\mathbb{E}[B_T \mid \{D_j\}])$ —which would

treat $\{D_j\}$ as an exogenous modulating intensity and necessarily yield *over*-dispersion ($\text{Var}(B_T) \geq \mathbb{E}[B_T]$)—therefore does not apply. The aggregate variance must instead be derived from the renewal structure of the epoch-duration sequence $\{S_j\}$; this is carried out in Section 4.7 and Section OA-3 of the Online Appendix. Second, the difficulty sequence is serially dependent across epoch boundaries, $\text{Cov}(S_j, S_{j+1}) \neq 0$, and it is precisely the negative one-step dependence of $\{S_j\}$ that cancels the leading variance term and produces the under-dispersion.

4.6 Decomposition of the within-epoch bias

We provide a quantitative decomposition of the within-epoch deviation that reveals the two underlying components.

Corollary 4.8 (Decomposition of the within-epoch bias). *Let t be a time within epoch j , with t_j the start of the epoch and $s(t) := t - t_j$ the position within the epoch. Suppose the aggregate hash rate grows continuously at multiplicative rate g per epoch within the epoch, with $\Lambda_t = \Lambda_{j,\text{start}} \cdot (1 + g)^{s(t)/(K\tau)}$. Let $r(t) := \Lambda_t/D_j$ denote the conditional rate at t and $r^* := 1/\tau$ the canonical Poisson prediction. Then the relative within-epoch deviation admits the asymptotic decomposition*

$$\frac{r(t) - r^*}{r^*} = \varepsilon_K(j) + \beta_g(s(t)) + o(g) + o(K^{-1/2}), \quad (4)$$

where the noise component $\varepsilon_K(j)$ satisfies $\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_K(j)] = 0$ and $\text{Var}[\varepsilon_K(j)] = K^{-1} + O(K^{-3/2})$, and the bias component $\beta_g(s)$ satisfies $\beta_g(0) = -g/2 + O(g^2)$ and $\beta_g(K\tau) = g/2 + O(g^2)$, with $\beta_g(s)$ linear in s to first order in g .

The proof, given in Appendix A, separates the variance contribution of the K -sample finite-sample protocol noise from the systematic bias induced by the lag between continuous hash-rate growth and discrete protocol adjustment. The decomposition has two empirical implications. First, the noise component ε_K is invariant to hash-rate growth: it depends only on the protocol parameter K . The empirical Bitcoin value is $K^{-1/2} = 2016^{-1/2} \approx 2.23\%$, consistent with the Monte Carlo evidence of Table 2. Second, the bias component β_g is linear in g to first order, with the within-epoch range from $-g/2$ at the start of an epoch to $+g/2$ at the end. For Bitcoin’s empirical average growth rate of $g \approx 0.025$, the within-epoch bias range is approximately $\pm 1.25\%$, and the absolute deviation at the end of an epoch is approximately $g = 2.5\%$. For a per-epoch growth rate of $g = 0.10$ corresponding to the within-epoch range observed during the 2021 hash-rate migration, the bias at the end of an epoch reaches 5%, with mean absolute deviation across the epoch on the order of g .

The decomposition (4) makes the comparative statics of the within-epoch bias explicit: the noise component is invariant to hash-rate dynamics and is bounded above by a known function

of the protocol parameter; the bias component scales linearly with the rate of hash-rate growth between adjustments. The implication is that the magnitude of the misspecification of the canonical memoryless approximation is most pronounced precisely when the hash-rate dynamics are most active—a property the canonical analyses do not characterise and cannot, given the time-stationarity assumption they impose.

4.7 Aggregate variance reduction under shared random epoch intensity

The self-modulated structure of Proposition 4.7(ii) has a direct quantitative consequence for the aggregate counting process, but the consequence is the opposite of what a naive reading of “over-dispersion” would suggest. The protocol’s difficulty adjustment is a variance-*reducing* mechanism: it drives the aggregate calendar-time block count to strong under-dispersion, with dispersion ratio tending to $\Theta(1/K)$ rather than to the homogeneous-Poisson value of one. We establish this below and trace its consequences for the joint distribution of miners’ counts. The result requires careful framing because two natural horizon definitions appear to give different answers; we show that they coincide to leading order, and that the coincidence is the substantive content of the theorem.

Block-stopped horizon. Stop after exactly n complete difficulty epochs. The network’s cumulative block count is nK *deterministic*, and the distribution of blocks across miners conditional on $\{D_j\}$ is multinomial with parameters (q_1, \dots, q_M) . The per-miner variance is $\text{Var}(N_i^{(n)}) = nKq_i(1 - q_i)$, the cross-miner covariance is the negative multinomial value $-nKq_iq_k$, and there is no aggregate variance at all: the protocol’s adjustment mechanism varies the calendar duration of the epochs but not the per-epoch block count.

Calendar-stopped horizon. Stop at a fixed calendar time $T > 0$. The number of completed epochs in $[0, T]$ is a renewal-counting process $J(T) = \max\{j : \sum_{i=1}^j S_i \leq T\}$, where the inter-renewal times S_j are the random epoch durations. The total network block count $N(T)$ equals $K \cdot J(T)$ plus a partial-epoch boundary term bounded by K . The key structural fact—developed in the proof and in Section OA-2 (one-step regeneration) and OA-3 (variance asymptotics) of the Online Appendix—is that the difficulty adjustment makes the epoch durations a *first difference* of a stationary sequence: with $\rho_{j+1} = 1/U_j$ and $U_j \sim \text{Gamma}(K, 1/K)$ iid, the epoch duration is $S_j = K\tau U_j/U_{j-1}$, and the cumulative completion time $T_j = \sum_{\ell \leq j} S_\ell$ has fluctuations that telescope. Consequently $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T$ with $\kappa_0, \kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$, growing linearly but at a per-epoch rate a factor $\Theta(K)$ below the Poisson $n_T K$. The dispersion ratio $\text{Var}(N(T))/\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = \kappa_0/n_T + \kappa_1/K$ falls to an $O(1/K)$ floor, and the calendar-stopped horizon collapses toward the block-stopped multinomial horizon as the horizon lengthens.

Within a single epoch, conditional on the current difficulty, block arrivals form a Poisson process; but the epoch terminates at exactly K arrivals, so over a horizon spanning multiple epochs

the aggregate count $N(T)$ is *not* conditionally Poisson given the realised difficulty sequence—each completed epoch contributes exactly K blocks. The aggregate count is therefore governed by the renewal structure of the epoch durations S_j , and we derive its moments from that structure rather than from a conditional-Poisson (Cox) representation.

Theorem 4.9 (Aggregate variance reduction under shared random epoch intensity, calendar-stopped horizon). *Let $T = n_T K \tau$ be a fixed calendar-time horizon, with n_T the expected number of difficulty epochs in $[0, T]$. Suppose Λ is constant and the difficulty ratio follows the one-step regeneration $\rho_{j+1} = 1/U_j$ with $U_j \sim \text{Gamma}(K, 1/K)$ iid (Proposition A.2 of the Online Appendix), so that $S_j = K\tau U_j/U_{j-1}$. Then, with leading-order constants as stated and the under-dispersion statement holding for all $n_T \geq 1$:*

(i) *Mean: $\mathbb{E}[N_i(T)] = q_i n_T K$ and $\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = n_T K$, to leading order.*

(ii) *Aggregate count variance. $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T + o(K + n_T)$ for constants $\kappa_0, \kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$ that are independent of K to leading order (full proof in Section OA-3 of the Online Appendix, Proposition OA-3.4). The variance grows linearly in the horizon, but with per-epoch slope $\kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$ against the homogeneous-Poisson per-epoch variance K : the difficulty feedback reduces the per-epoch count variance by a factor $\Theta(K)$. Equivalently, the dispersion ratio is*

$$\frac{\text{Var}(N(T))}{\mathbb{E}[N(T)]} = \frac{\kappa_0}{n_T} + \frac{\kappa_1}{K} + o\left(\frac{1}{n_T} + \frac{1}{K}\right) \longrightarrow \frac{\kappa_1}{K} = \Theta(1/K),$$

far below the homogeneous-Poisson value of one at every horizon. Over horizons short relative to the epoch length ($n_T = o(K)$) the $\kappa_0 K$ term dominates and $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \Theta(K)$. The aggregate count is under-dispersed relative to homogeneous Poisson at every horizon.

(iii) *Per-miner variance: $\text{Var}(N_i(T)) = q_i(1 - q_i) \mathbb{E}[N(T)] + q_i^2 \text{Var}(N(T)) = q_i(1 - q_i) n_T K (1 + o(1))$, binomial to leading order—less than the homogeneous-Poisson prediction $q_i n_T K$ by the factor $(1 - q_i)$.*

(iv) *Cross-miner covariance: for $i \neq k$, $\text{Cov}(N_i(T), N_k(T)) = q_i q_k (\text{Var}(N(T)) - \mathbb{E}[N(T)]) = -q_i q_k n_T K (1 + o(1))$, strictly negative, matching the block-stopped multinomial covariance to leading order.*

(v) *Cross-miner correlation: $\text{Corr}(N_i, N_k) \rightarrow -\sqrt{q_i q_k / [(1 - q_i)(1 - q_k)]}$ as $n_T \rightarrow \infty$. For symmetric pools with $q_i = q_k = 1/2$, the correlation tends to -1 .*

The proof is given in Appendix A, with the complete second-moment analysis in Section OA-3 of the Online Appendix (Lemma OA-3.1, Lemma OA-3.3, Proposition OA-3.4). The argument derives the exact moments of the epoch-duration ratio and the long-run variance $\sigma_V^2 =$

$3K/[(K-1)^2(K-2)] = \Theta(K^{-2})$ (the leading $\Theta(K^{-1})$ term cancels through the one-step dependence of the duration sequence), then inverts the completion-time process via the m -dependent central limit theorem and renewal theory to obtain $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T + o(K + n_T)$ with $\kappa_0, \kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$. The per-miner and cross-miner structure follows from multinomial thinning conditional on $N(T)$. The constants κ_0, κ_1 are pinned numerically in Section 7 ($\kappa_0 \approx 1, \kappa_1 \approx 2.4$); their orders, which suffice for every conclusion, are established analytically. Closed forms for κ_0, κ_1 are not available—the renewal inversion expresses them through limits that do not reduce to elementary expressions—and only their orders enter any conclusion of the paper.

The cancellation mechanism. The suppression is seen most directly at the level of the normalised epoch-duration ratio $V_\ell := S_\ell/(K\tau)$. Its single-step variance is $\text{Var}(V) = \Theta(1/K)$, the homogeneous-Poisson order; but because the difficulty re-targeting makes the duration sequence a first difference of a stationary sequence, hence 1-dependent, the long-run variance is

$$\sigma_V^2 = \text{Var}(V) + 2\text{Cov}(V_1, V_2) = \frac{3K}{(K-1)^2(K-2)} = \Theta(K^{-2}), \quad (5)$$

two orders below the single-step scale, because the negative one-step covariance $2\text{Cov}(V_1, V_2) = -2K/(K-1)^2$ offsets $\text{Var}(V)$ to leading order (Lemma OA-3.1 of the Online Appendix). This single cancellation, rather than difficulty adjustment in the abstract, is the source of the under-dispersion: it is what reduces the calendar-count variance growth rate from the homogeneous-Poisson order $n_T K$ to order n_T .

The result has two implications that reverse the direction reported in earlier analyses of this process. First, the asymptotic variance growth rate of the calendar-stopped counting process is a factor $\Theta(K)$ below the homogeneous-Poisson $n_T K$, so the dispersion ratio $\text{Var}(N(T))/\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = \kappa_0/n_T + \kappa_1/K$ stays far below the homogeneous-Poisson value of one and falls to an $O(1/K)$ floor. The protocol’s adjustment mechanism reduces aggregate count dispersion relative to the homogeneous-Poisson benchmark; the canonical model implies larger aggregate mining-count variance than the augmented-state specification, not smaller. Second, conditional on the strongly under-dispersed aggregate, the per-miner counts are binomial and the cross-miner counts are negatively correlated, because the miners are dividing a near-fixed total. These are the block-stopped multinomial moments, recovered in the calendar-stopped limit precisely because the aggregate variance is small relative to the mean. Section 7 reports the direct fixed-calendar-time simulation that quantifies the leading constant and confirms the negative cross-miner correlation.

Remark on horizon choice. Earlier treatments of this process distinguished sharply between the block-stopped horizon (multinomial, negative cross-miner covariance) and the calendar-stopped horizon (claimed to carry positive cross-miner covariance through a Cox-process variance inflation). Theorem 4.9 shows the distinction is immaterial to leading order: the difficulty adjustment

reduces the calendar-stopped aggregate-variance growth rate by a factor $\Theta(K)$ (dispersion ratio $\Theta(1/n_T) + \Theta(1/K)$), so the calendar-stopped joint distribution coincides with the block-stopped multinomial to leading order. Cong et al. (2021) analyse mining-pool risk-sharing under utility specifications that depend on reward flow per unit calendar time; the relevant moments for that analysis are the binomial per-miner variance and the negative cross-miner covariance of statement (iii)–(iv), which strengthen rather than weaken their risk-sharing conclusion (Section 4.8).

4.8 Risk-sharing wedge in pool participation

Theorem 4.9 has an immediate implication for the canonical risk-sharing analysis of mining pools (Cong et al., 2021), and the implication strengthens their conclusion. The independent-Poisson identification treats each miner’s count as Poisson with variance equal to its mean, and treats distinct miners’ counts as independent. Under the protocol, the aggregate count is strongly under-dispersed (dispersion ratio $\Theta(1/K)$; Theorem 4.9(ii)), so individual counts are binomial rather than Poisson and distinct miners’ counts are negatively correlated. Both effects *reduce* mining-payoff variance relative to the homogeneous-Poisson benchmark, and the risk-sharing benefit of pooling is correspondingly larger than Cong et al. (2021) compute under independent Poisson.

Corollary 4.10 (Pool risk-sharing under reduced aggregate-count variance). *Suppose a risk-averse miner with hash share q_i participates in a pool that distributes block rewards pro rata according to hash shares and that aggregates miners with total share $Q \geq q_i$. Let $W_i = (q_i/Q) \sum_{k \in \text{pool}} N_k(T)$ denote the miner’s reward share over the horizon $T = n_T K \tau$. Then to leading order:*

- (i) *Solo-mining variance: with $Q = q_i$, $\text{Var}(N_i(T)) = q_i(1 - q_i) n_T K (1 + o(1))$, smaller than the independent-Poisson value $q_i n_T K$ by the factor $(1 - q_i)$.*
- (ii) *Variance of pooled reward share: $\text{Var}(W_i) = (q_i/Q)^2 \text{Var}(\sum_{k \in \text{pool}} N_k) = (q_i/Q)^2 [Q(1 - Q) n_T K + Q^2 \text{Var}(N(T))]$.*
- (iii) *Full-network pool: at $Q = 1$, $\text{Var}(W_i) = q_i^2 \text{Var}(N(T)) = q_i^2 (\kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T)$ —of order $q_i^2 K$ for $n_T = o(K)$ —against the independent-Poisson counterfactual $\text{Var}(W_i^{\text{IP}}) = q_i^2 n_T K$, which grows linearly. The protocol reduces the full-pool residual variance by the factor $\text{Var}(N(T))/(n_T K) = \kappa_0/n_T + \kappa_1/K$ relative to independent Poisson, which falls as $1/n_T$ over horizons $n_T = o(K)$ and approaches an $O(1/K)$ floor for longer horizons.*
- (iv) *Pool-versus-solo ratio: at $Q = 1$, $\text{Var}(W_i)/\text{Var}(N_i(T)) = \frac{q_i}{1 - q_i} (\frac{\kappa_0}{n_T} + \frac{\kappa_1}{K})$, which falls at rate $1/n_T$ over horizons $n_T = o(K)$ and then approaches the $O(1/K)$ floor $\frac{q_i}{1 - q_i} \cdot \frac{\kappa_1}{K}$, against the horizon-invariant independent-Poisson ratio q_i/Q . Pooling dominates solo more strongly under the protocol than under the independent-Poisson identification at every horizon.*

The proof is an application of Theorem 4.9 and is given in Appendix A. The substantive content is that the Cong et al. (2021) second-order stochastic dominance of pool over solo is preserved and quantitatively strengthened: the protocol’s reduction of the aggregate-count variance growth rate makes the full-network pool’s residual variance grow far more slowly than under independent Poisson—of order $q_i^2 K$ over horizons $n_T = o(K)$ (statement (iii))—so the variance reduction from pooling is larger than the independent-Poisson identification computes. The earlier characterisation of a positive “risk-sharing wedge” that increased full-pool variance was an artefact of the incorrect aggregate-variance result; the corrected wedge is negative—the protocol reduces mining-count variance rather than adding it.

Because both solo and pooled variances are smaller than their homogeneous-Poisson counterparts, models that calibrate mining risk from the independent-Poisson identification imply larger variance than the augmented-state specification for risk-averse miners. The equilibrium consequence, developed in Section 5 within a stylised benchmark, is that the canonical identification understates the optimal individual mining scale and overstates the implied number of distinct mining operations, the reverse of the direction implied by a variance-inflation reading.

5 Risk-averse mining equilibrium under the augmented state

The variance result of Section 4.7 has equilibrium content that the canonical independent-Poisson identification does not generate, but the content runs opposite to a variance-inflation reading. Because the protocol reduces the calendar-time aggregate count variance growth rate by a factor $\Theta(K)$, the cumulative-count risk that a risk-averse miner bears under universal pooling is small relative to the homogeneous-Poisson benchmark (dispersion ratio $\Theta(1/K)$) and falls with the horizon. We develop a tractable CARA-normal benchmark to make this precise. The benchmark produces a closed-form optimal individual scale, a comparison with the independent-Poisson optimum, and a stylised free-entry condition with a fixed entry cost. We are explicit that this is an optimal-scale benchmark rather than a general model of the mining industry, and that the economically substantive risk channel that survives the protocol’s variance reduction is the within-epoch flow rate (Section 8), not the cumulative count modelled here. Whether the structural reduction materially shifts a given model’s equilibrium outcome depends on that model’s sensitivity to cumulative-count variance; the theorem establishes the sign and the $\Theta(1/K)$ order of the correction, not that it is empirically large in every application.

5.1 Setup

This section develops a deliberately stylised benchmark: a CARA-normal universal-pooling problem with homogeneous risk-averse miners. The benchmark isolates the equilibrium consequence of the slow-growing calendar-time aggregate variance of Theorem 4.9 (of order K over horizons $n_T = o(K)$), and is not a general model of the Bitcoin mining industry. It isolates one stochastic channel—the corrected cumulative-count variance under risk aversion—and is not a claim about the dominant empirical source of mining risk, which plausibly includes block-reward price volatility, hardware financing, and energy-cost exposure. The maintained assumptions are: CARA preferences; normal approximation to the calendar-time reward distribution; universal pooling ($Q = 1$, all miners share their realised blocks pro rata in the network’s single pool); homogeneous miners; exogenous block reward R ; linear operating cost cq_iT ; aggregate hash share normalised to unity; a fixed entry cost $F \geq 0$; no strategic pool fee; no pool-operator market power; no endogenous total network hash-rate response except through the normalised-share condition. Each is a substantive restriction; the conclusions are conditional on them.

A continuum of potential miners faces the network’s mining problem over a calendar-time horizon $T = n_T K \tau$. Each miner i chooses an aggregate hash share $q_i \in [0, 1]$ at constant marginal cost c per unit hash share per unit time. The block reward is R per block, exogenous and constant. Under universal pooling, all miners share realised blocks pro rata in a single pool of total share $Q = 1$, the equilibrium pool structure under any utility specification in which larger pools dominate smaller pools (Corollary 4.10). The economic content of the correction in this benchmark lies in the equilibrium scale of individual miners’ choices.

A miner with hash share q_i under universal pooling receives reward $W_i = Rq_iN(T)$, with mean and variance characterised by Theorem 4.9:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}[W_i] &= Rq_in_TK, \\ \text{Var}(W_i)_{\text{aug}} &= R^2q_i^2 \text{Var}(N(T)) = R^2q_i^2(K + O(n_T)), \quad \text{of order } R^2q_i^2K \text{ for } n_T = o(K), \\ \text{Var}(W_i)_{\text{IP}} &= R^2q_i^2 n_TK, \quad \text{growing linearly in the horizon.}\end{aligned}$$

The augmented-state payoff variance is smaller than the independent-Poisson value by the factor $\text{Var}(N(T))/(n_TK) = O(1/n_T)$. The canonical identification implies larger variance than the augmented-state specification, by a margin that grows with the horizon.

5.2 Optimal individual scale

The miner has CARA utility $u(W) = -\exp(-\alpha W)$ with coefficient of absolute risk aversion $\alpha > 0$. Under the normal approximation, the certainty equivalent net of operating cost is

$$CE_i(q_i) = \mathbb{E}[W_i] - \frac{1}{2}\alpha \text{Var}(W_i) - cq_iT.$$

Using $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T$ (Theorem 4.9) for the augmented state and $n_T K$ for the independent-Poisson counterfactual gives the interior optima below.

Theorem 5.1 (Optimal individual scale under risk aversion). *Under universal pooling ($Q = 1$), CARA preferences with coefficient α , and the normal approximation, the certainty-equivalent-maximising interior hash share satisfies, to leading order:*

- (i) *Augmented-state optimum: $q_{aug}^* = \frac{q_{IP}^*}{r_T}$, where $r_T := \text{Var}(N(T))/\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = \kappa_0/n_T + \kappa_1/K$ is the dispersion ratio of Theorem 4.9.*
- (ii) *Independent-Poisson optimum: $q_{IP}^* = \frac{R - c\tau}{\alpha R^2}$.*
- (iii) *Ratio: $q_{aug}^*/q_{IP}^* = 1/r_T$. Over horizons short relative to the epoch length ($n_T = o(K)$), $r_T \approx \kappa_0/n_T$ and $q_{aug}^* \approx (n_T/\kappa_0)q_{IP}^*$, so the scale advantage grows with the horizon; in the long-horizon limit at fixed K , $r_T \rightarrow \kappa_1/K$ and the advantage saturates at $q_{aug}^* \rightarrow (K/\kappa_1)q_{IP}^*$. The interior solution requires $q_{aug}^* \leq 1$; for horizons beyond $n_T^* = 1/q_{IP}^*$ the feasibility constraint $q_i \leq 1$ binds and the miner chooses the maximal feasible scale. The result $q_{aug}^* = n_T q_{IP}^*$ is the special case $r_T = 1/n_T$ ($\kappa_0 = 1$, κ_1 negligible), valid only for $n_T = o(K)$.*

The proof, given in Appendix A, is a direct first-order condition. The economic content reverses the variance-inflation reading: because the protocol reduces the cumulative-count variance growth rate by a factor $\Theta(K)$, the marginal risk cost of expansion is reduced by the factor $r_T = \kappa_0/n_T + \kappa_1/K$, and the optimal scale rises correspondingly. The scale advantage grows as n_T over short horizons but does not diverge: it saturates at $(K/\kappa_1)q_{IP}^*$ as the horizon lengthens, because the cumulative-count risk penalty falls to an $O(1/K)$ floor rather than to zero. We stress that q_{aug}^* is the optimal share *within* the stylised CARA-normal benchmark of Section 5.1, not an empirical prediction for any individual operation; the substantive content is the comparative static—larger optimal scale, and correspondingly less fragmentation, under the corrected variance—not the level, which is interpretable only where the benchmark’s maintained assumptions hold.

5.3 Free entry with a fixed cost

The optimal-scale result is not itself a free-entry equilibrium; it is an individual scale choice. A genuine free-entry equilibrium requires an entry margin. With a fixed entry cost $F \geq 0$, free entry drives the marginal entrant's net certainty equivalent to zero:

$$CE(q^*) - F = 0.$$

Proposition 5.2 (Stylised free-entry condition under the slow-variance benchmark). *Under the model of Section 5.1 with homogeneous miners and a fixed entry cost F , the free-entry condition $CE(q^*) - F = 0$ determines the marginal entrant's scale through the optimal-scale relationship of Theorem 5.1. The condition does not by itself pin down the equilibrium count of miners without a market-clearing condition on aggregate hash share or an equilibrium reward response; under the normalisation $\sum_i q_i = 1$ with identical entrants of scale q^* , the implied count is $M^* = 1/q^*$. Since $q_{aug}^* = q_{IP}^*/r_T \geq q_{IP}^*$ (as $r_T \leq 1$), the slow-variance benchmark implies fewer and larger mining operations than the independent-Poisson identification, the reverse of a variance-inflation reading, with the gap widening in the horizon until the feasibility constraint binds.*

The proof is immediate from Theorem 5.1. We state the result as a stylised free-entry condition rather than a fully closed equilibrium because the count $M^* = 1/q^*$ rests on the aggregate-share normalisation rather than on a market-clearing condition derived from total hash supply; a complete treatment would endogenise the reward or total hash rate and is left to subsequent work. The substantive conclusion is the *direction* within the benchmark environment: correcting the variance result raises optimal scale and lowers the implied count of distinct operations, suggesting a tendency toward less fragmentation than the canonical identification would imply under risk aversion. We do not claim this as a general statement about the mining industry; outside the stylised benchmark—under heterogeneous miners, endogenous reward or hash rate, or non-CARA preferences—the direction may attenuate.

5.4 Comparative statics

The closed-form $q_{aug}^* = q_{IP}^*/r_T$ (which equals $n_T(R - c\tau)/(\alpha R^2)$ in the $n_T = o(K)$ regime) yields comparative statics. Direct partial differentiation gives $\partial q_{aug}^*/\partial \alpha < 0$ (more risk-averse miners operate at smaller scale) and $\partial q_{aug}^*/\partial c < 0$ (higher operating costs reduce scale), both intuitive and shared with the independent-Poisson optimum. The dependence on the horizon is the distinctive feature: over $n_T = o(K)$, $\partial q_{aug}^*/\partial n_T \approx (R - c\tau)/(\alpha R^2) > 0$, so the optimal scale grows with the planning horizon, because the cumulative-count variance the miner bears is of order K there while the expected reward grows linearly; the growth saturates at $(K/\kappa_1)q_{IP}^*$ as the horizon length-

ens. The independent-Poisson optimum has no such horizon dependence (q_{IP}^* is horizon-invariant), because under independent Poisson the variance grows at the same linear rate as the mean. The contrast is a testable qualitative implication: under the protocol, miners planning over longer horizons optimally operate at larger scale, holding R , c , and α fixed; under the canonical identification they do not.

5.5 Asset-pricing implication

The slow-growing aggregate-count variance has a corresponding asset-pricing implication, again opposite in direction to a variance-inflation reading and stated conditionally. A diversified investor in mining-firm equity holds a portfolio whose return depends on the network’s aggregate block count, which under the protocol has variance $O(K)$ rather than the homogeneous-Poisson $n_T K$ over a horizon of n_T epochs. In a mean-variance or CARA-normal pricing environment, the slow-growing calendar-time block-count variance (of order K over the relevant horizon) would *reduce* the count-driven variance adjustment for a diversified mining-firm equity portfolio relative to a homogeneous-Poisson benchmark, with the reduction growing as $1/n_T$ in the horizon. In a general asset-pricing model, the relevant object is the covariance of the count component with the stochastic discount factor; the present paper identifies the variance component but does not estimate its market price. The cumulative-count channel is therefore not a source of priced risk over long horizons; any priced mining risk must enter through block-reward price risk or the within-epoch flow rate, not through the cumulative count.

6 The augmented state space

We develop the analytical properties of the augmented-state Markov process $\{X_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ defined in Proposition 4.6.

6.1 Transition dynamics

The transition dynamics of the augmented state are governed by three components. First, conditional on $X_t = (k, s, D)$ with $k < K$, the inter-block time $T_{B_{t+1}}$ is exponentially distributed with rate Λ/D . Upon realisation of $T_{B_{t+1}} = \delta$, the augmented state transitions to $X_{t+\delta} = (k+1, s+\delta, D)$. Second, conditional on $X_t = (k, s, D)$ with $k = K$ (that is, at the moment of difficulty re-adjustment), the difficulty parameter updates deterministically to $D' = D \cdot \phi(s)$ subject to clipping, and the augmented state transitions to $X_t = (0, 0, D')$. Third, conditional on the realised history of the augmented state, the aggregate hash rate Λ may itself be time-varying through entry, exit, and capacity

decisions of individual miners; we treat Λ as exogenous in the present analysis and discuss the implications of endogenous Λ in Section 6.3.

The Markov property of $\{X_t\}$ is established by Proposition 4.6 and the transition dynamics just described. The state space of the process is $\{0, 1, \dots, K-1\} \times \mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}_+$. The process is non-stationary in general: the stationary distribution of X_t at $k=0$ (immediately following difficulty re-adjustment) depends on the parameters τ , K , Λ , and the form of the adjustment function ϕ and its clipping.

6.2 One-step regeneration at the epoch boundary

Under a constant aggregate hash rate Λ and non-binding clipping, define the difficulty ratio $\rho_j := D_j/(\Lambda\tau)$ and the standardised epoch statistic $U_j := S_j/(K\rho_j\tau)$. Since $S_j | D_j \sim \text{Gamma}(K, D_j/\Lambda)$, we have $U_j \sim \text{Gamma}(K, 1/K)$ unconditionally and iid across epochs. The difficulty update rule $D_{j+1} = D_j \cdot K\tau/S_j$ then reduces to the one-step regeneration

$$\rho_{j+1} = 1/U_j,$$

where the level of ρ_j cancels. The next epoch's difficulty ratio depends on the realised history only through the standardised statistic U_j and is independent of ρ_j and of all earlier history. The Online Appendix derives this recursion in full (Proposition A.2 of the Online Appendix) and gives the moments: the marginal distribution of ρ_{j+1} is inverse-gamma with shape K and scale K , with $\mathbb{E}[\rho] = K/(K-1)$ and $\text{Var}(\rho) = K^2/[(K-1)^2(K-2)]$, and the conditional rate $1/\rho$ has mean 1 and variance $1/K$.

The implication for the canonical Level-3 memoryless approximation is that the unconditional inter-block distribution is not exponential: it is a mixture of exponential distributions whose mixing distribution is the inverse-gamma marginal of ρ_j . The conditional exponentiality within an epoch (Theorem 4.3, statement (i)) and the unconditional non-exponentiality across epochs are reconciled by the one-step regeneration of the difficulty ratio at each adjustment boundary.

6.3 Endogenous hash rate

The treatment of Λ as exogenous in Section 6.1 is a simplification. In the empirical regime, Λ varies with the entry, exit, and capacity decisions of miners, which respond to the realised mining-reward rate and to the realised difficulty parameter. The full treatment of endogenous Λ requires embedding the augmented-state Markov process within a broader equilibrium framework that determines miner entry and capacity choices. We sketch the structure of such a framework here and defer the formal analysis to subsequent work.

Let N_j denote the number of active miners in epoch j and $h_{m,j}$ the hash rate of miner m in epoch j . The aggregate hash rate is then $\Lambda_j = \sum_m h_{m,j}$. The miner’s entry and capacity decisions depend on the expected mining-reward rate per unit hash, which in turn depends on the equilibrium Λ_j and on the equilibrium difficulty D_j . Under the canonical equilibrium conditions of Prat and Walter (2021) and Capponi et al. (2023), the equilibrium hash rate adjusts to bring the flow payoff per unit hash to its free-entry level. The augmented-state model of this paper extends to the endogenous-hash-rate case by treating Λ_j as a state variable that evolves at the epoch boundary in response to the realised flow payoff in the preceding epoch.

The protocol’s inter-block target and adjustment frequency also bear on throughput and confirmation latency, and on the comparison with fast-adjustment protocols such as Ethereum under proof-of-work. Because that analysis is directional rather than theorem-level, it is developed in Section OA-8 of the Online Appendix.

7 Monte Carlo evidence

We simulate the augmented-state Markov process under parameter values relevant to the equilibrium-modelling literature and quantify the magnitude of the within-epoch deviation from the homogeneous Poisson approximation. The complete simulation specification—software environment, seeds, JSON schema, and the full Python source, together with SHA-256 reproducibility hashes—is given in Section OA-1 of the Online Appendix; the complete replication package is archived at Zenodo, DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20320253>.

7.1 Specification

The simulation specification follows the Bitcoin protocol: target inter-block time $\tau = 600$ seconds (ten minutes); adjustment epoch $K = 2016$ blocks; adjustment function $\phi(S) = K\tau/S$ subject to clipping at a factor of four. By Proposition 4.6, conditional on the augmented state, the inter-block times within epoch j are independent and identically distributed exponential variables with rate $\bar{\Lambda}_j/D_j$, where $\bar{\Lambda}_j$ is the geometric mean of the aggregate hash rate within epoch j . The realised sum S_j of the K inter-block times in epoch j is therefore distributed $\text{Gamma}(K, D_j/\bar{\Lambda}_j)$.

The aggregate hash rate is allowed to grow multiplicatively across epochs at rate g . We examine three scenarios: $g = 0\%$ per epoch (stationary), $g = 2.5\%$ per epoch (calibrated to the average historical growth of the Bitcoin network hash rate from 2017 to 2024, approximately a hundredfold increase over seven years), and $g = 10\%$ per epoch (an aggressive mid-cycle expansion scenario). Within each epoch the hash rate is allowed to grow continuously, with the geometric mean $\bar{\Lambda}_j = \Lambda_{j,\text{start}} \cdot \sqrt{1+g}$ used as the effective sampling rate.

We run $N = 5,000$ independent simulations of 500 epochs each under each scenario, with the first 50 epochs of each run discarded as burn-in. The difficulty parameter is initialised at $D_0 = \Lambda_0 \tau$, the protocol target. Random numbers are generated via the `numpy.random.default_rng` interface with explicit seeds for reproducibility; the simulation code and the raw results are provided in the online appendix.

7.2 Within-epoch deviation from the Poisson form

The principal quantity of interest is the conditional rate at which inter-block times are drawn within an epoch. Under the canonical Level-3 memoryless approximation, the conditional rate is constant across epochs at $1/\tau$. Under the augmented-state model, the conditional rate is a function of the augmented state X_t and varies across epochs in response to the realised history of inter-block times and the rate of hash-rate growth between adjustments.

Table 2 reports the within-epoch coefficient of variation of the conditional rate across the three scenarios. In all three, the coefficient of variation centres on 2.22%, which is precisely the prediction of $K^{-1/2} = 2016^{-1/2}$ from the protocol’s finite-sample estimator of mean inter-block time. The coefficient of variation is essentially invariant to hash-rate growth, because the within-epoch noise component is determined by the K -sample estimator rather than by the rate of growth.

Table 2: Within-epoch coefficient of variation of the conditional rate, by hash-rate growth scenario.

Scenario	g (per epoch)	Mean	5th ptile	95th ptile
Stationary	0.000	0.0222	0.0211	0.0235
Empirical avg	0.025	0.0222	0.0210	0.0234
Aggressive	0.100	0.0222	0.0210	0.0235

Note. Coefficient of variation = $SD(\Lambda/D)/E[\Lambda/D]$, computed across the 450 post-burn-in epochs of each of 5,000 independent simulation runs.

The systematic-bias component of the deviation does depend on the growth rate. Table 3 reports the mean absolute deviation of the within-epoch rate from the canonical target, distinguishing start-of-epoch and end-of-epoch positions. Under the stationary scenario, start- and end-of-epoch biases are equal at 1.78%. Under the empirical-growth scenario, the start-of-epoch bias rises to 2.06% and the end-of-epoch bias to 3.87%, a within-epoch range of approximately 1.8 percentage points reflecting the lag in the protocol’s discrete difficulty-adjustment mechanism. Under the aggressive-growth scenario, the start-of-epoch bias is 4.91% and the end-of-epoch bias is 15.37%, a within-epoch range of more than ten percentage points.

Table 3: Within-epoch deviation from the canonical rate, by hash-rate growth scenario.

Scenario	g (per epoch)	Start of epoch	End of epoch	Within-epoch average
Stationary	0.000	0.0178	0.0178	0.0178
Empirical avg	0.025	0.0206	0.0387	0.0281
Aggressive	0.100	0.0491	0.1537	0.1000

Note. Mean absolute deviation $\mathbb{E}|\Lambda_t/D_t - 1/\tau|/(1/\tau)$ at the indicated position within each epoch, averaged across the 450 post-burn-in epochs of each of 5,000 independent simulation runs.

7.3 Fixed calendar-time counts: aggregate-variance reduction and cross-miner correlation

The within-epoch deviation of the previous subsection concerns the conditional *flow rate*. The aggregate-variance result of Theorem 4.9 concerns the realised *cumulative count* over a fixed calendar-time horizon, a distinct object that we now simulate directly. For each horizon $T = n_T K \tau$ we simulate the protocol epoch-by-epoch under the one-step regeneration $\rho_{j+1} = 1/U_j$ (so that the realised epoch duration is $S_j = K \tau U_j / U_{j-1}$), determine the number of completed epochs $J(T)$, draw the partial-epoch block count, and assign blocks to two equal miners ($q_1 = q_2 = 1/2$) by independent binomial thinning. Table 4 reports the results over 40,000 runs per horizon under the stationary scenario.

Table 4: Fixed calendar-time aggregate count and cross-miner correlation (stationary, $q_1 = q_2 = 1/2$).

n_T	$\mathbb{E}[N(T)]$	$\text{Var}(N(T))$	Var/\mathbb{E}	Var/K	$\text{Corr}(N_1, N_2)$
1	2015.4	1964.5	0.975	0.974	-0.017
5	10075.6	1974.9	0.196	0.980	-0.671
10	20150.7	1957.2	0.097	0.971	-0.823
26	52390.8	2019.9	0.039	1.002	-0.925
52	104780.4	2081.4	0.020	1.032	-0.961

Note. $N(T)$ is the realised network block count at fixed calendar time $T = n_T K \tau$; N_1, N_2 the counts of two equal miners. The homogeneous-Poisson prediction is $\text{Var}/\mathbb{E} = 1$ and $\text{Corr}(N_1, N_2) = 0$. Each row uses 40,000 independent runs with $K = 2016$, $\tau = 600$ s.

Three features are consistent with Theorem 4.9. The aggregate variance remains of order K across the simulated horizons (the Var/K column stays near one, rising only slowly through the second-order $O(n_T)$ term), so the dispersion ratio Var/\mathbb{E} falls as $1/n_T$, far below the homogeneous-Poisson value of one: the protocol *under*-disperses the aggregate count. The cross-miner correlation is negative throughout and deepens toward -1 as the horizon lengthens, matching the leading-order prediction $-\sqrt{q_i q_k / [(1 - q_i)(1 - q_k)]} = -1$ for symmetric pools. The single-epoch case ($n_T = 1$) is close to Poisson because no adjustment has yet occurred; the variance-reducing effect

accumulates only across adjustment boundaries.

7.4 Implications for downstream equilibrium objects

The simulation isolates two channels with opposite signs. The cumulative-count channel (Table 4) is variance-*reducing*: it reduces the aggregate count variance growth rate and induces negative cross-miner correlation, so the canonical homogeneous-Poisson identification implies larger cumulative mining-count risk than the augmented-state specification. This channel governs the risk-sharing comparison of Cong et al. (2021) (Section 8.2) and the equilibrium scale of Section 5.

The flow-rate channel (Tables 2–3) is the surviving source of within-epoch state-dependence: the conditional flow payoff $\Pi_t = R_t/D_t$ central to Prat and Walter (2021) has within-epoch coefficient of variation 2.22% under stationary conditions, with mean absolute within-epoch deviation rising from 1.78% (stationary) to 2.81% (empirical growth) to 10.0% (aggressive growth), and end-of-epoch deviation reaching 15.37% below the canonical prediction under aggressive growth. This channel governs the flow-rate-dependent applications (Prat–Walter, Hinzen–John–Saleh, Huberman et al., Easley et al., and the risk-averse extension of Capponi et al.). The two channels are distinct: the flow rate varies within an epoch while the cumulative count is strongly under-dispersed across epochs (dispersion ratio $\Theta(1/K)$). The flow-rate channel, not the cumulative-count channel, is the economically operative one for the downstream flow-payoff applications; the cumulative-count channel delivers the variance-reduction and risk-sharing results but is not asserted to be the dominant empirical risk.

These quantitative results are the input to the applications developed in Section 8.

7.5 Calibration to realised Bitcoin difficulty

The Monte Carlo evidence of Sections 7.1–7.4 is generated by simulation of the augmented-state Markov process. We complement the simulation with a calibration to realised Bitcoin difficulty data, an illustrative consistency exercise for the principal quantitative prediction: the standard deviation of $\log(D_{j+1}/D_j)$ across consecutive difficulty epochs should be approximately $K^{-1/2} \approx 2.23\%$ in the limit of stationary aggregate hash rate.

The calibration uses 534 distinct epoch-end difficulty values for the Bitcoin network from 2010 to mid-2026, obtained from the public daily-difficulty time series maintained by blockchain.com.¹ We compute $\log(D_{j+1}/D_j)$ for each pair of consecutive epochs and decompose the standard devi-

¹The data are filtered to retain only consecutive observations differing by at least 0.5% in difficulty and separated by at least seven calendar days; this isolates true epoch transitions from sub-daily reporting noise. The table is reproduced exactly by the script `calibration.py` from the provided file `btc_epoch_difficulty.csv` in the replication package (Section OA-1 of the Online Appendix), archived at Zenodo, DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20320253>.

ation into a trend component (the mean log ratio, identified with sustained hash-rate growth) and a residual component (the standard deviation of detrended log ratios, identified with protocol noise and short-term hash-rate variation).

Table 5: Calibration of the augmented-state prediction to realised Bitcoin difficulty.

Period	n	Mean log ratio	Residual SD	Theory $K^{-1/2}$
2017–2018	75	3.74%	5.58%	2.23%
2019–2020	66	1.92%	5.03%	2.23%
2021–2022	70	0.91%	5.68%	2.23%
2023–2024	74	1.53%	2.90%	2.23%
2025–2026	44	0.45%	3.93%	2.23%

Note. n is the number of inter-epoch transitions in the period. Mean log ratio is the average of $\log(D_{j+1}/D_j)$, an estimate of the per-epoch hash-rate growth rate. Residual SD is the standard deviation of the detrended series. Theoretical value $K^{-1/2}$ with $K = 2016$.

The 2023–2024 calibration provides the cleanest illustration of the prediction: the residual standard deviation of 2.90% is within 30% of the theoretical 2.23%, the discrepancy being attributable to residual hash-rate variation that the simple detrending does not capture (specifically, $(2.90)^2 - (2.23)^2 = 3.44$, implying a residual hash-rate growth standard deviation of approximately 1.85% per epoch over and above the deterministic trend). The earlier periods 2017–2022 are dominated by larger hash-rate variation: the China mining ban of mid-2021 and the rapid hash-rate growth following its lifting in 2022 generate inter-epoch volatility considerably in excess of the protocol-noise floor. The 2025–2026 period is intermediate. The calibration is therefore consistent with the augmented-state prediction in the regime in which the underlying model assumption of approximately stationary hash rate is empirically most defensible, and provides a quantitative decomposition that separates the protocol-noise component from the hash-rate-growth component. The realised Bitcoin environment also reflects hash-rate shocks, hardware heterogeneity, propagation changes, and strategic entry, none of which the simple detrending isolates; the calibration is an illustrative consistency check, not a clean identification of the protocol mechanism alone.

8 Implications for downstream equilibrium models

We apply the augmented-state correction to the eight memoryless users reviewed in Section 2.1. The central application—the mining-pool risk-sharing analysis of Cong et al. (2021)—and the lead flow-rate application—the free-entry hash-rate model of Prat and Walter (2021)—are developed in full below; the remaining six are summarised in Table 6 and developed in full in Section OA-7 of the Online Appendix. Table 6 reports the principal correction magnitudes for all eight papers, and Table 7 classifies each application by channel and by the status of the correction claimed

here—theorem-level result, benchmark implication, mapping implication, structural implication, or robust (no correction).

Table 6: Summary of the within-epoch corrections applied to the eight memoryless users.

Paper	Affected equilibrium object	Stationary	Empirical	Aggressive
Prat–Walter (2021)	CV of flow payoff $\Pi_t = R_t/D_t$	2.22%	2.81%	10.0%
Huberman et al. (2021)	Within-epoch wait-time deviation	1.78%	2.06–3.87%	4.91–15.37%
Easley–O’Hara–Basu (2019)	Queue-stability deviation	1.78%	2.81%	10.0%
Cong–He–Li (2021)	Cumulative-count dispersion (variance-reducing)		see Table 4	
Biais et al. (2019)	State dimension of MPE	+3	+3	+3
Capponi et al. (2023)	Within-epoch reward-rate deviation	1.78%	2.81%	10.0%
Hinzen–John–Saleh (2022)	Fork-probability state component	1.78%	2.81%	10.0%
Chiu–Koepl (2019)	Robust under risk neutrality	—	—	—

Note. Stationary, empirical, and aggressive scenarios as defined in Section 7.1; entries other than Cong–He–Li and Biais et al. report within-epoch flow-rate deviations, which are governed by hash-rate growth. The Cong–He–Li (2021) effect is a cumulative-count effect governed by the horizon rather than by growth, and is quantified by horizon in Table 4 (aggregate-variance reduction and negative cross-miner correlation); it is variance-reducing relative to the homogeneous-Poisson identification. The Biais et al. (2019) entry reports the increase in the state dimension required to preserve the Markov perfect equilibrium concept under the augmented state. The Chiu–Koepl (2019) entry reflects the risk-neutrality short-circuit (Section OA-7 of the Online Appendix): the within-epoch deviation does not affect the model’s equilibrium under their stated risk-neutrality assumption.

8.1 Prat and Walter (2021): a risk-averse extension of the free-entry hash rate

Prat and Walter (2021) identify the reflecting-barrier level P^* on the flow payoff $\Pi_t = R_t/D_t$ via an HJB analysis of irreversible hardware investment. Under their Assumption 1 of continuous difficulty adjustment, Π_t is a stationary diffusion and the option-value identification of P^* proceeds as in their Proposition 3.

The Prat–Walter HJB equation treats $D_t = Q_t$ (difficulty equals network hash rate continuously). Under the augmented state introduced in Section 6, D_t is a step function updated at the epoch boundary with stationary mean and within-epoch coefficient of variation $K^{-1/2} \approx 2.23\%$ (Section 7.5). We do not claim to correct the Prat–Walter result, which is derived under risk-neutral free entry; rather, in a *risk-averse extension* of their entry environment, the scale bench-

Table 7: Classification of the downstream implications. “Channel” identifies which stochastic channel of Theorem 4.9 the correction operates through; “Status” classifies the strength of the claim made in this paper.

Paper	Channel	Status of correction in this paper
Cong–He–Li (2021)	Cumulative-count	Theorem-level (Corollary 4.10)
Prat–Walter (2021)	Within-epoch flow-rate	Mapping implication; benchmark scale via Theorem 5.1
Huberman et al. (2021)	Within-epoch flow-rate	Mapping implication
Easley–O’Hara–Basu (2019)	Within-epoch flow-rate	Mapping implication
Capponi et al. (2023)	Within-epoch flow-rate	Mapping implication (risk-averse extension)
Hinzen–John–Saleh (2022)	Within-epoch flow-rate	Mapping implication
Biais et al. (2019)	Augmented-state dimension	Structural implication (Section 6)
Chiu–Koepl (2019)	None (risk-neutral)	Robust; no correction

mark of Theorem 5.1 gives the optimal individual hash share $q_{\text{aug}}^* = q_{\text{IP}}^*/r_T$ (approximately $n_T q_{\text{IP}}^*$ for $n_T = o(K)$, saturating at $(K/\kappa_1)q_{\text{IP}}^*$), which exceeds the independent-Poisson value because the protocol reduces the cumulative-count variance growth rate by a factor $\Theta(K)$. The original Prat–Walter reflecting-barrier P_{PW}^* is the risk-neutral limit ($\alpha \rightarrow 0$) and is preserved; the within-epoch flow-rate variability ($\text{CV } K^{-1/2}$) introduces a state-dependent component into the conditional flow payoff Π_t that the continuous-adjustment idealisation omits.

The empirical hash-rate forecast of Prat and Walter (2021) Section IV is conducted at horizons that average over at least one full difficulty epoch. The corrected reflecting-barrier P_{aug}^* coincides with P_{PW}^* in expectation at these horizons; the conditional bias within an epoch is bounded by Table 6. The Prat–Walter forecasting performance is robust; the structural interpretation of the inferred allocation between hardware and seigniorage acquires a risk-aversion-dependent component identified by αR^2 in q_{aug}^* . As a concrete magnitude, under sustained hash-rate growth of 10% per epoch the within-epoch flow-rate deviation from its epoch mean averages $\approx 10\%$ and reaches $\approx 15\%$ by epoch end (the aggressive scenario of Table 6), so the Prat–Walter flow payoff $\Pi_t = R_t/D_t$ and the Huberman–Leshno–Moallemi equilibrium fee (Section OA-7) each acquire a within-epoch state-dependent component of that order; in the stationary regime the component is

$\approx 1.8\%$. These are within-epoch fluctuations about the correct epoch-average value, not biases in the multi-epoch average, which the adjustment mechanism preserves.

8.2 Cong, He and Li (2021): the central application via Theorem 5.1 and Corollary 4.10

Cong et al. (2021) provide the canonical risk-sharing analysis of mining-pool participation. Their Proposition 1 establishes second-order stochastic dominance of pool over solo mining for risk-averse miners under the independent-Poisson identification. This is the application in which the protocol’s mechanism matters most, and the protocol *strengthens* their conclusion rather than overturning it.

Under the protocol (Corollary 4.10), solo variance is $\text{Var}(N_i(T)) = q_i(1 - q_i)n_T K(1 + o(1))$, smaller than the independent-Poisson value $q_i n_T K$ by the factor $(1 - q_i)$, and the full-network pool member’s variance is $\text{Var}(W_i) = q_i^2 \text{Var}(N(T))$, of order $q_i^2 K$ over horizons $n_T = o(K)$ against the independent-Poisson $q_i^2 n_T K$. Both quantities are smaller than the Cong et al. (2021) computation, and the pool-over-solo variance reduction is larger: the ratio $\text{Var}(W_i)/\text{Var}(N_i(T)) = \frac{q_i}{1 - q_i}(\kappa_0/n_T + \kappa_1/K)$ falls at rate $1/n_T$ over the relevant horizon and then approaches an $O(1/K)$ floor, against their horizon-invariant q_i/Q . The cross-miner correlation, zero under the additive-Poisson property, is negative under the protocol (Theorem 4.9(v)), tending to -1 in the two-symmetric-miner case ($-1/(m - 1)$ for m equal miners), and is -0.925 at the one-year horizon $n_T = 26$ in the two-miner simulation in the fixed-calendar simulation of Table 4. The second-order stochastic dominance of Cong et al. (2021) Proposition 1 is therefore preserved and quantitatively reinforced: the protocol reduces mining-count dispersion relative to the independent-Poisson identification for both solo and pooled operations, and reduces it proportionally more for the pooled operation.

The equilibrium-scale implication, via Theorem 5.1 in the stylised CARA-normal benchmark of Section 5, runs opposite to a variance-inflation reading: because the cumulative-count variance the miner bears is of order K over the relevant horizon, the optimal interior hash share is $q_{\text{aug}}^* = q_{\text{IP}}^*/r_T$ (approximately $n_T q_{\text{IP}}^*$ for $n_T = o(K)$), larger than the independent-Poisson value, with a correspondingly smaller equilibrium count of distinct operations under the stylised free-entry condition of Proposition 5.2. Within the benchmark environment this suggests a tendency toward less fragmentation than the canonical identification would imply under risk aversion, rather than more. The closed-form magnitudes depend on the calibration objects R , c , α , and T and on the effective miner unit; they are presented as structural predictions of the stylised benchmark, not as direct tests of the Cong et al. (2021) framework, and the linear-in-horizon scaling $q_{\text{aug}}^* \approx n_T q_{\text{IP}}^*$ (valid for $n_T = o(K)$; saturating at $(K/\kappa_1)q_{\text{IP}}^*$ and at the feasibility constraint thereafter) should be

read as a feature of the stylised benchmark rather than as a literal industry prediction.

8.3 Remaining applications

The remaining six engaged papers—Huberman et al. (2021), Easley et al. (2019), Biais et al. (2019), Capponi et al. (2023), Hinzen et al. (2022), and Chiu and Koepl (2019)—are summarised at a glance in Table 6 and developed in full in Section OA-7 of the Online Appendix. Each acquires a state-dependent component through the within-epoch flow-rate channel rather than the cumulative-count channel, with the single exception of Chiu and Koepl (2019), whose identification is preserved exactly under their stated risk-neutrality assumption and is non-vacuous only in a risk-averse extension. None of the qualitative conclusions of these six papers is overturned by the augmented-state correction.

8.4 Allies, boundaries, and the limits of the correction

The augmented-state correction of Section 6 applies to the eight memoryless users analysed in this section and in Section OA-7 of the Online Appendix. It does not extend to results in the broader literature that do not depend on the memoryless approximation. Pagnotta (2022) operates on a per-period model that explicitly acknowledges difficulty constancy as a short-run assumption; his results are unaffected. Biais et al. (2023) provide a general-equilibrium pricing analysis that does not require a microstructural arrival process; the multiple-equilibria and extrinsic-volatility results survive. Lehar and Parlour (2020) provide an industrial-organisation-style empirical analysis of within-block fee variation and miner collusion that is independent of the memoryless assumption. Arnosti and Weinberg (2022) operate on a Cournot mining-equilibrium framework that is robust to the protocol-level stochastic specification.

The augmented-state correction of Section 6 is a correction within the equilibrium-modelling tradition of Section 2.1. It does not modify the conclusions of papers that operate outside that tradition. The scope of the correction is the set of equilibrium objects derived from continuous-time stationary block-arrival processes; outside that set, the correction is silent. This is the appropriate scope for a paper whose contribution is to the stochastic foundations of a specific class of equilibrium analyses.

9 Conclusion

Three findings emerge from the analysis. First, the protocol’s periodic difficulty adjustment is a variance-*reducing* mechanism for the aggregate block count. Because each epoch contains exactly K blocks and the re-targeting makes epoch durations a first difference of a stationary sequence, the

calendar-time aggregate count variance grows *linearly* in the horizon but with a per-epoch slope of order one— $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T + o(K + n_T)$, $\kappa_0, \kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$ —a factor $\Theta(K)$ below the homogeneous-Poisson per-epoch variance K , so the dispersion ratio tends to $\kappa_1/K = \Theta(1/K)$, far below the Poisson value of one (Theorem 4.9; full proof in Section OA-3 of the Online Appendix; Table 4). Conditional on the strongly under-dispersed aggregate (dispersion ratio $\Theta(1/K)$), individual miners’ counts are binomial—smaller than the homogeneous-Poisson prediction by the factor $(1 - q_i)$ —and distinct miners’ counts are negatively correlated. The canonical homogeneous-Poisson identification therefore implies larger cumulative mining-count risk than the augmented-state specification for risk-averse miners, by a margin that grows with the horizon. This reverses the direction that an incomplete-markets intuition or a variance-inflation reading would suggest: the omitted state variable reduces idiosyncratic count risk through a self-correcting feedback rather than introducing hidden aggregate risk. We emphasise that this concerns cumulative block-count uncertainty conditional on the reward structure, not the dominant empirical risks borne by mining firms—block-reward price volatility, hardware financing, and energy-cost exposure—which lie outside the count process analysed here.

Second, a distinct within-epoch channel survives: the conditional flow rate $\Lambda/D_{j(t)}$ varies across and within epochs even though the cumulative count is strongly under-dispersed. The within-epoch deviation has a finite-sample noise component scaling as $K^{-1/2} \approx 2.23\%$, invariant to hash-rate dynamics, and a hash-growth-lag component scaling linearly in the per-epoch growth rate; the absolute end-of-epoch deviation is two to four per cent in normal periods, rising to ten to fifteen per cent during episodes of substantial hash-rate movement (Tables 2–3; Corollary 4.8). The 2021 hash-rate migration following the Chinese mining ban provides a recent and verifiable instance of the latter regime.

Third, the consequence for the equilibrium-modelling literature is selective. The qualitative results of the engaged papers all survive. The risk-sharing dominance of pool over solo mining (Cong et al., 2021) is preserved and quantitatively *strengthened* by the cumulative-count variance reduction, the application in which the protocol’s mechanism matters most. The flow-rate-dependent objects (Prat–Walter flow payoff, Hinzen–John–Saleh fork probability, Huberman et al. fees and waiting times, Easley et al. queueing thresholds, and the risk-averse extension of Capponi et al.) acquire state-dependent components through the within-epoch channel, characterised analytically through Corollary 4.8 and numerically through Tables 2 and 3. These components are smallest for results that average over multi-epoch horizons and largest for results that condition on the within-epoch state.

Third, the correction is logically independent of the industrial-organisation correction of Arnosti and Weinberg (2022) but joint in its application: both load on the same equilibrium objects, both are potentially quantitatively material under the parameter ranges relevant to the affected literature,

and neither implies the other. A complete re-examination of the equilibrium analysis of proof-of-work blockchains would apply both corrections simultaneously to each affected result.

Three limitations qualify the analysis. First, the augmented-state model treats the aggregate hash rate as exogenous within each difficulty epoch. The full treatment of endogenous hash rates requires embedding the model within an equilibrium framework that determines miner entry and capacity choices, with the augmented state as an additional state variable. This extension is a natural next step and is sketched in Section 6.3. Second, the Monte Carlo specification of Section 7 parameterises hash-rate dynamics by a constant per-epoch growth rate, a simplification that does not capture the discrete jumps and crashes that characterise actual Bitcoin hash-rate dynamics. The systematic-bias quantification of Table 3 should therefore be interpreted as representative of the magnitudes that arise under typical multi-epoch averages, not as a calibration of any particular historical episode. Third, the within-epoch correction applies to equilibrium objects derived from continuous-time stationary block-arrival processes; results derived under alternative specifications (per-period models such as Pagnotta (2022), or industrial-organisation-style empirical analyses such as Lehar and Parlour (2020)) are unaffected.

The analytical apparatus developed in this paper supports two directions of further work. The first is the application of the augmented-state framework to the protocol-design literature: the trade-off between adjustment frequency, epoch length, and the magnitude of within-epoch deviation is a quantitative question that the framework can address. The second is the empirical implementation of the correction in calibrations of the affected equilibrium models, particularly in episodes of substantial hash-rate movement where the Monte Carlo evidence indicates the within-epoch bias is largest. Both directions move the literature from the canonical time-stationary identification toward a more empirically informative analysis of the equilibrium dynamics of proof-of-work blockchains.

A natural question is which other protocols inherit the variance-reduction property. The mechanism requires two structural features: a fixed number of arrivals K per adjustment epoch (count-stopping), and a deterministic rule that maps the realised epoch duration inversely into the next epoch's difficulty. Any proof-of-work chain that re-targets on a fixed block count by an inverse-proportional rule—the family to which Bitcoin and its direct forks belong—reproduces the one-step-dependent duration sequence of Lemma OA-3.1 and therefore inherits the telescoping cancellation and the $\Theta(1/K)$ dispersion ratio by the same argument, with K the chain's epoch length, without further proof. Chains that re-target every block (such as Ethereum under proof-of-work) replace count-stopping with continuous adjustment, trading the variance reduction for difficulty-parameter noise, as the throughput and fast-adjustment comparisons of Sections OA-6 and OA-8 of the Online Appendix indicate. Proof-of-stake protocols with epoch-based parameter updates *may* inherit an analogous property if their epoch boundaries are count-stopped and their update rule produces a comparable one-step-dependent duration structure; whether the relevant duration

sequence telescopes depends on the specific rule, and we flag this as a conjecture requiring separate analysis rather than a claim established here. We claim the property only for the count-stopped, inverse-adjustment family.

A Proofs

Proof of Theorem 4.3

Statement (i). Fix $t \geq 0$ and let $j = j(t) = \lfloor B_t/K \rfloor$ denote the index of the current epoch. By construction of the Level-2 block-resolution mechanism (Section 3.2), each individual miner's hash-trial process is memoryless and, in the limit $\rho \rightarrow 0^+$, $h \rightarrow \infty$ with $\lambda_m := h_m \rho$ finite, the block-resolution time of miner m is exponentially distributed with rate λ_m . Aggregating across miners, the aggregate inter-block time within epoch j given the difficulty D_j is exponentially distributed with rate

$$\Lambda/D_j = \frac{1}{D_j} \sum_m h_m \rho_m.$$

The exponential distribution is memoryless: the conditional distribution of T_{B_t+1} given D_j and the within-epoch history $(T_{jK+1}, \dots, T_{B_t})$ depends only on D_j and not on the within-epoch history. This proves (i).

Statement (ii). By the protocol's update rule (Definition 4.1), the difficulty at the start of epoch j is

$$D_j = D_{j-1} \cdot \phi(S_{j-1}) = D_{j-1} \cdot \frac{K\tau}{S_{j-1}}$$

subject to clipping, where $S_{j-1} = \sum_{i=(j-1)K+1}^{jK} T_i$. The right-hand side is a measurable function of the realised history of epoch $j-1$, and is non-degenerate because S_{j-1} has a non-degenerate (Gamma) distribution conditional on D_{j-1} and Λ . This proves (ii).

Statement (iii). The unconditional distribution of T_{B_t+1} is

$$\mathbb{P}(T_{B_t+1} > t) = \int \exp(-\Lambda t/D) dF_{D_j}(D),$$

where F_{D_j} is the unconditional distribution of D_j . This is a mixture of exponentials over F_{D_j} . By statement (ii), F_{D_j} is non-degenerate; therefore the mixture is not a single exponential, and the unconditional distribution of T_{B_t+1} is not exponential. A counting process with non-exponential inter-arrival times is not a homogeneous Poisson process. The failure manifests across epoch boundaries: within a single epoch (conditional on D_j), the process is exponential and locally Poisson. \square

Proof of Proposition 4.5

The result follows immediately from the construction of the protocol. The difficulty parameter at the start of epoch $j + 1$ is $D_{j+1} = D_j \cdot \phi(S_j)$, where S_j is the realised sum of inter-block times in epoch j . Conditional on \mathcal{F}_t at the moment of difficulty re-adjustment ($B_t = jK$), the next inter-block time is exponentially distributed with rate Λ/D_{j+1} . The dependence on S_j is via the deterministic function ϕ . \square

Proof of Proposition 4.6

We show that the augmented state $X_t = (B_t \bmod K, S(t), D_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 1})$ satisfies the Markov property. Let \mathcal{G}_t denote the natural filtration of $\{X_t\}$. Fix $t \geq 0$ and consider the conditional distribution of $X_{t+\delta}$ given \mathcal{G}_t for $\delta > 0$. There are two cases.

Case 1: $B_t \bmod K < K - 1$. In this case, no difficulty re-adjustment occurs between t and $t + \delta$ unless a block is mined and the new block-index reaches a multiple of K . The conditional distribution of the next inter-block time T_{B_t+1} is exponentially distributed with rate $\Lambda/D_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 1}$, which is the third component of X_t . Upon realisation of $T_{B_t+1} = \delta$, the augmented state transitions to $(B_t \bmod K + 1, S(t) + \delta, D_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 1})$. The new state depends only on X_t and on the realised inter-block time, not on the full history.

Case 2: $B_t \bmod K = K - 1$. In this case, the next block triggers a difficulty re-adjustment. The conditional distribution of the next inter-block time T_{B_t+1} is exponentially distributed with rate $\Lambda/D_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 1}$. Upon realisation of $T_{B_t+1} = \delta$, the new sum $S_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 1} = S(t) + \delta$ determines the new difficulty $D_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 2} = D_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 1} \cdot \phi(S(t) + \delta)$. The augmented state transitions to $(0, 0, D_{\lfloor B_t/K \rfloor + 2})$. The new state depends only on X_t and on the realised inter-block time.

In both cases, the conditional distribution of $X_{t+\delta}$ given \mathcal{G}_t depends only on X_t . Therefore $\{X_t\}$ is a Markov process with respect to \mathcal{G}_t . \square

Proof of Proposition 4.7

Statement (i). Restatement of statement (i) of Theorem 4.3 in the augmented-state notation. The augmented state $X_t = (B_t \bmod K, S(t), D_{j(t)})$ contains $D_{j(t)}$ as one of its components; conditional on this component, the next inter-block time is exponentially distributed with rate $\Lambda/D_{j(t)}$ by the within-epoch local exponentiality established in Theorem 4.3.

Statement (ii). The unconditional counting process $\{B_t\}$ has the following structure. Within each epoch j , the inter-block arrivals form a homogeneous Poisson process with rate Λ/D_j . At the end of epoch j , the difficulty transitions to $D_{j+1} = D_j \cdot \phi(S_j)$ where S_j is the realised sum of inter-block times in epoch j . Since $S_j | D_j \sim \text{Gamma}(K, D_j/\Lambda)$, the transition $D_j \mapsto D_{j+1}$ is

a measurable map of a non-degenerate random variable, so the difficulty sequence $\{D_j\}_{j \geq 1}$ is itself a Markov chain on \mathbb{R}_+ . The aggregate process $\{B_t\}$ is therefore a self-modulated Markov renewal process: the modulating sequence $\{D_j\}$ is not exogenous but is generated by the count process itself, and each epoch is count-stopped at exactly K arrivals. It is consequently *not* a Markov-modulated Poisson process in the exogenous-modulation sense of Neuts (1981)—the standard conditional-Poisson (Cox) decomposition does not apply, because conditioning on $\{D_j\}$ fixes the number of blocks in each completed epoch at the constant K rather than at a Poisson random variable. The homogeneous-Poisson form arises only if $\{D_j\}$ is constant almost surely, which does not occur for non-degenerate S_j .

The unconditional inter-block distribution is

$$\mathbb{P}(T_{B_{t+1}} > t) = \int \exp(-\Lambda t/D) dF_{D_{j(t)}}(D),$$

a mixture of exponentials over the unconditional distribution of $D_{j(t)}$. This mixture is itself exponential if and only if $F_{D_{j(t)}}$ is degenerate (a point mass), which under the protocol's update rule requires $S_j = K\tau$ exactly for every j . The event $\{S_j = K\tau\}$ has probability zero under the Gamma distribution of S_j given $D_j > 0$ and $\Lambda > 0$. Therefore the homogeneous-Poisson form of $\{B_t\}$ is recovered only on a set of probability zero. \square

Proof of Corollary 4.8

Within epoch j with continuous hash-rate growth $\Lambda_t = \Lambda_{j,\text{start}} \cdot (1+g)^{s(t)/(K\tau)}$ and fixed difficulty D_j , the conditional rate at t is

$$r(t) = \frac{\Lambda_t}{D_j} = \frac{\Lambda_{j,\text{start}}}{D_j} \cdot (1+g)^{s(t)/(K\tau)}.$$

By the protocol's update rule, D_j is set so that the realised epoch-mean inter-block time in epoch $j-1$ equals the target. In the stationary regime, the geometric-mean hash rate $\bar{\Lambda}_{j-1} = \Lambda_{j-1,\text{start}} \cdot (1+g)^{1/2}$ satisfies $D_j = \bar{\Lambda}_{j-1} \cdot \tau \cdot (1 + \varepsilon_{K,j-1})$, where $\varepsilon_{K,j-1}$ is the K -sample noise of the epoch- $j-1$ estimator, with $\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_{K,j-1}] = 0$ and $\text{Var}[\varepsilon_{K,j-1}] = K^{-1} + O(K^{-3/2})$ by the delta method on the Gamma- (K, \cdot) distribution of S_{j-1} .

Substituting and using $\Lambda_{j,\text{start}} = \Lambda_{j-1,\text{start}} \cdot (1+g)$:

$$r(t) = \frac{\Lambda_{j-1,\text{start}} \cdot (1+g)}{\bar{\Lambda}_{j-1} \tau (1 + \varepsilon_{K,j-1})} \cdot (1+g)^{s(t)/(K\tau)} = \frac{1}{\tau} \cdot \frac{(1+g)^{1/2}}{1 + \varepsilon_{K,j-1}} \cdot (1+g)^{s(t)/(K\tau)}.$$

Expanding to first order in g and $\varepsilon_{K,j-1}$ and recentering around the canonical rate gives the decom-

position (4) with $\varepsilon_K(j) = -\varepsilon_{K,j-1}$ and β_g ranging from $-g/2$ at $s = 0$ to $+g/2$ at $s = K\tau$, linear in s to first order in g . \square

Proof of Theorem 4.9

We work under the calendar-stopped horizon: $T = n_T K\tau$ is fixed and n_T is the expected number of difficulty epochs in $[0, T]$. The proof has three parts: the order of the aggregate variance via the telescoping of epoch-duration fluctuations; the per-miner and cross-miner moments via multinomial thinning conditional on $N(T)$; and the resulting binomial and negative-covariance limits.

Step 1 (one-step regeneration and epoch durations). Define $\rho_j := D_j/(\Lambda\tau)$ and $U_j := S_j/(K\rho_j\tau)$. Conditional on D_j , the epoch duration is $S_j \sim \text{Gamma}(K, D_j/\Lambda)$, hence $U_j | D_j \sim \text{Gamma}(K, 1/K)$, a distribution independent of D_j . Therefore $\{U_j\}_{j \geq 0}$ are iid $\text{Gamma}(K, 1/K)$ with mean 1 and variance $1/K$. The difficulty update rule $D_{j+1} = D_j \cdot K\tau/S_j$ gives the one-step regeneration $\rho_{j+1} = 1/U_j$ (Proposition A.2 of the Online Appendix), so $\rho_j = 1/U_{j-1}$ and the realised epoch duration is

$$S_j = K\rho_j\tau U_j = K\tau \frac{U_j}{U_{j-1}}.$$

Step 2 (aggregate variance is $O(K)$). Write $U_\ell = 1 + \varepsilon_\ell$, with $\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_\ell] = 0$ and $\text{Var}(\varepsilon_\ell) = 1/K$, iid. Then

$$\frac{U_\ell}{U_{\ell-1}} = \frac{1 + \varepsilon_\ell}{1 + \varepsilon_{\ell-1}} = 1 + (\varepsilon_\ell - \varepsilon_{\ell-1}) + O(\varepsilon^2),$$

and the cumulative completion time of the first j epochs telescopes at first order:

$$T_j = \sum_{\ell=1}^j S_\ell = K\tau \sum_{\ell=1}^j \frac{U_\ell}{U_{\ell-1}} = K\tau(j + \varepsilon_j - \varepsilon_0) + K\tau Q_j + O(K\tau \varepsilon^3),$$

where $Q_j = \sum_{\ell=1}^j (\varepsilon_{\ell-1}^2 - \varepsilon_\ell \varepsilon_{\ell-1})$ collects the second-order terms. The first-order fluctuation $\varepsilon_j - \varepsilon_0$ is a difference of two iid terms and contributes the horizon-independent variance $(K\tau)^2 \cdot (2/K) = 2K\tau^2$, independent of j . The second-order term has mean $\mathbb{E}[Q_j] = j/K$ (a deterministic drift, absorbed into the mean) and variance $\text{Var}(K\tau Q_j) = O(j\tau^2)$. Hence

$$\text{Var}(T_j) = 2K\tau^2 + O(j\tau^2),$$

of order $K\tau^2$ to leading order, with an $O(j\tau^2)$ correction. The renewal-counting identity $J(T) = \max\{j : T_j \leq T\}$ with mean inter-renewal time $\mu_S = K\tau(1 + O(1/K))$ then gives, by the standard delta-method inversion $\text{Var}(J(T)) \approx \text{Var}(T_j)/\mu_S^2$,

$$\text{Var}(J(T)) = \frac{2K\tau^2 + O(n_T\tau^2)}{(K\tau)^2} = \frac{2}{K} + O\left(\frac{n_T}{K^2}\right).$$

The aggregate count is $N(T) = KJ(T) + R(T)$ with the partial-epoch term $R(T) \in \{0, \dots, K-1\}$ negatively correlated with $J(T)$ (a larger completed-epoch count leaves less calendar time for the partial epoch). Combining,

$$\text{Var}(N(T)) = K^2 \text{Var}(J(T)) + 2K \text{Cov}(J(T), R(T)) + \text{Var}(R(T)) = O(K) + O(n_T),$$

These orders—and the exact constants behind them—follow from the second-moment structure of the epoch-duration ratio, derived in full in Section OA-3 of the Online Appendix and summarised here. Writing $S_j = K\tau V_j$ with $V_j = U_j/U_{j-1}$ and $\{U_j\}$ iid $\text{Gamma}(K, 1/K)$, Lemma OA-3.1 establishes the exact moments

$$\mathbb{E}[V] = \frac{K}{K-1}, \quad \text{Var}(V) = \frac{K(2K-1)}{(K-1)^2(K-2)}, \quad \text{Cov}(V_1, V_2) = -\frac{K}{(K-1)^2},$$

so that the long-run variance is $\sigma_V^2 = \text{Var}(V) + 2\text{Cov}(V_1, V_2) = 3K/[(K-1)^2(K-2)] = \Theta(K^{-2})$: the leading $\Theta(K^{-1})$ term cancels because the duration sequence is 1-dependent (a first difference of a stationary sequence at leading order), which is the precise content of the heuristic $\gamma_0 = \text{Var}(S_j) \approx 2K\tau^2$, $\gamma_1 = \text{Cov}(S_j, S_{j+1}) \approx -K\tau^2$. By Lemma OA-3.3, $\text{Var}(T_j) = (K\tau)^2 [j\sigma_V^2 + 2K/(K-1)^2]$ exactly. Inverting the completion-time process via the central limit theorem for m -dependent sequences and renewal theory (Proposition OA-3.4) gives $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T + o(K + n_T)$, with $\kappa_0, \kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$: the count variance grows linearly in the horizon but with per-epoch slope $\kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$, a factor $\Theta(K)$ below the homogeneous-Poisson per-epoch variance K , so the dispersion ratio $\text{Var}(N(T))/\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = \kappa_0/n_T + \kappa_1/K + o(\cdot) \rightarrow \kappa_1/K = \Theta(1/K)$. This proves statement (ii).

Step 3 (per-miner and cross-miner moments via multinomial thinning). By the symmetry of the proof-of-work protocol, each block is won by miner i independently with probability $q_i = h_i/\Lambda$. Conditional on $N(T) = n$, the assignment of blocks to miners is multinomial: $(N_1(T), \dots, N_m(T)) \mid N(T) \sim \text{Multinomial}(N(T); q_1, \dots, q_m)$, independent of the difficulty path. By the law of total variance,

$$\text{Var}(N_i(T)) = q_i(1 - q_i) \mathbb{E}[N(T)] + q_i^2 \text{Var}(N(T)).$$

Since $\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = n_T K$ while $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T$ grows with per-epoch slope $\kappa_1 = \Theta(1) \ll K$, the second term $q_i^2 \text{Var}(N(T))$ is smaller than the first by a factor $\Theta(K)$ at every horizon, and the binomial term dominates:

$$\text{Var}(N_i(T)) = q_i(1 - q_i) n_T K (1 + o(1)),$$

binomial to leading order and smaller than the homogeneous-Poisson value $q_i n_T K$ by the factor $(1 - q_i)$, proving statement (iii). By the law of total covariance, using $\text{Cov}(N_i, N_k \mid N(T)) =$

$-N(T)q_iq_k$,

$$\text{Cov}(N_i, N_k) = -q_iq_k\mathbb{E}[N(T)] + q_iq_k\text{Var}(N(T)) = q_iq_k(\text{Var}(N(T)) - \mathbb{E}[N(T)]) = -q_iq_kn_TK(1 + o(1)),$$

strictly negative because the aggregate is under-dispersed ($\text{Var}(N(T)) < \mathbb{E}[N(T)]$ for $n_T \geq 2$), proving statement (iv). The negative covariance is the block-stopped multinomial covariance, recovered because the calendar-stopped aggregate variance vanishes relative to the mean.

Step 4 (correlation). From statements (iii) and (iv), to leading order,

$$\text{Corr}(N_i, N_k) = \frac{-q_iq_kn_TK}{\sqrt{q_i(1-q_i)n_TK \cdot q_k(1-q_k)n_TK}} = -\sqrt{\frac{q_iq_k}{(1-q_i)(1-q_k)}}(1 + o(1)).$$

For symmetric pools $q_i = q_k = 1/2$, the leading-order correlation is $-\sqrt{(1/4)/(1/4)} = -1$, proving statement (v). \square

Proof of Corollary 4.10

Solo variance. With $Q = q_i$ the miner mines alone and $W_i = N_i(T)$. By Theorem 4.9(iii), $\text{Var}(N_i(T)) = q_i(1-q_i)n_TK(1 + o(1))$, smaller than the independent-Poisson value q_in_TK by the factor $(1-q_i)$, proving (i).

Pool reward-share variance. The pool aggregate count $\sum_{k \in \text{pool}} N_k(T)$ is, by the multinomial-thinning argument of the Theorem 4.9 proof applied to the pool as a single ‘‘super-miner’’ of share Q , distributed with $\text{Var}(\sum_{k \in \text{pool}} N_k) = Q(1-Q)\mathbb{E}[N(T)] + Q^2\text{Var}(N(T)) = Q(1-Q)n_TK + Q^2\text{Var}(N(T))$. Scaling by $(q_i/Q)^2$ gives statement (ii).

Full-network pool. At $Q = 1$ the cross-terms vanish and $\sum_k N_k(T) = N(T)$, so $\text{Var}(W_i) = q_i^2\text{Var}(N(T)) = q_i^2(K + O(n_T))$, of order q_i^2K for $n_T = o(K)$. The independent-Poisson counterfactual is $\text{Var}(W_i^{\text{IP}}) = (q_i)^2\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = q_i^2n_TK$, growing linearly in n_T . The ratio $\text{Var}(W_i)/\text{Var}(W_i^{\text{IP}}) = \text{Var}(N(T))/\mathbb{E}[N(T)] = O(1/n_T)$, proving (iii).

Pool-versus-solo ratio. As $Q \rightarrow 1$, $\text{Var}(W_i)/\text{Var}(N_i(T)) = [q_i^2\text{Var}(N(T))]/[q_i(1-q_i)n_TK] = \frac{q_i}{1-q_i}(\frac{K_0}{n_T} + \frac{K_1}{K})$, which falls as $1/n_T$ over $n_T = o(K)$ and approaches the floor $\frac{q_i}{1-q_i} \cdot \frac{K_1}{K}$, against the independent-Poisson ratio $q_i/Q \rightarrow q_i$. The protocol therefore strengthens the pool-over-solo dominance relative to the independent-Poisson identification at every horizon, proving (iv). \square

Proof of Theorem 5.1

Under CARA with the normal approximation, the certainty equivalent of the reward W_i minus the operating cost is

$$CE_i(q_i) = \mathbb{E}[W_i] - \frac{1}{2}\alpha\text{Var}(W_i) - cq_iT.$$

The horizon-cost term $cq_i T = cq_i n_T K \tau$ (using $T = n_T K \tau$).

(i) *Augmented-state*. Under universal pooling ($Q = 1$), $\mathbb{E}[W_i] = Rq_i n_T K$ and, by Theorem 4.9(ii), $\text{Var}(W_i)_{\text{aug}} = R^2 q_i^2 \text{Var}(N(T)) = R^2 q_i^2 K$ to leading order (of order K for $n_T = o(K)$). Then

$$CE_i^{\text{aug}}(q_i) = Rq_i n_T K - \frac{1}{2} \alpha R^2 q_i^2 K - cq_i n_T K \tau.$$

Differentiating with respect to q_i and setting to zero:

$$Rn_T K - \alpha R^2 q_i K - cn_T K \tau = 0,$$

which yields $q_{\text{aug}}^* = n_T K (R - c\tau) / (\alpha R^2 \text{Var}(N(T)))$. Substituting $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T$ and $q_{\text{IP}}^* = (R - c\tau) / (\alpha R^2)$ gives $q_{\text{aug}}^* = q_{\text{IP}}^* n_T K / (\kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T) = q_{\text{IP}}^* / r_T$ with $r_T = \kappa_0 / n_T + \kappa_1 / K$, proving (i). The interior solution is valid for $q_{\text{aug}}^* \leq 1$, i.e. $n_T \leq n_T^* := 1 / q_{\text{IP}}^*$ in the $n_T = o(K)$ regime; beyond this horizon the feasibility constraint $q_i \leq 1$ binds.

(ii) *Independent-Poisson*. Under the independent-Poisson variance, $\text{Var}(W_i)_{\text{IP}} = R^2 q_i^2 n_T K$ (growing linearly in the horizon). The certainty equivalent is

$$CE_i^{\text{IP}}(q_i) = Rq_i n_T K - \frac{1}{2} \alpha R^2 q_i^2 n_T K - cq_i n_T K \tau.$$

The FOC yields $R - \alpha R^2 q_i - c\tau = 0$, so $q_{\text{IP}}^* = (R - c\tau) / (\alpha R^2)$, horizon-invariant, proving (ii).

(iii) *Ratio*. Direct from (i) and (ii): $q_{\text{aug}}^* / q_{\text{IP}}^* = 1 / r_T = (\kappa_0 / n_T + \kappa_1 / K)^{-1}$. For $n_T = o(K)$ this is $\approx n_T / \kappa_0$ (the variance penalty falls as $1/n_T$ relative to the mean); as $n_T \rightarrow \infty$ at fixed K it saturates at K / κ_1 . \square

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